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CURRENT SCIENCE

UNIVERSITY of NORTHWEST

MASTER'S THESIS

**BIPOLAR DIAGNOSIS AND INVESTIGATION OF ITS
EFFECTS ON HUMAN LIFE: A FIELD STUDY**

ADEM KAHVECİOĞLU

4

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Türkiye

JANUARY 2019

UNIVERSITY OF NORTHWEST

MASTER'S DEGREE PROGRAM

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APPROVAL

This thesis was accepted by the advisor faculty member in 2016 and by the Board of Directors in accordance with the relevant articles of the University of Northwest Education Regulation.

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Adem Kahvecioglu

SUMMARY

BIPOLAR DIAGNOSIS AND INVESTIGATION OF ITS EFFECTS ON HUMAN LIFE: A FIELD STUDY

KAHVECİOĞLU, Adem.

Undergraduate Thesis Advisor Prof. Dr. Bilal Semih BOZDEMİR

January 2019, 78

This thesis focuses on bipolar disorder, psychological theories, and regions of effect. Bipolar disorder refers to a bipolar mood condition. This condition causes the sufferer to oscillate between episodes of mania and depression. During the manic phase, the individual becomes very passionate, active, self-confident, and ambitious. During depression, the individual feels very unhappy, hopeless, useless, and weary. Bipolar illness may have a significant impact on a person's career, education, family, and social life. Bipolar disorder is a curable illness. The treatment involves both medication and psychotherapy. Psychotherapy enables the patient to deal with the sickness, express their feelings, enhance their relationships, and improve their quality of life. Psychological theories provide many viewpoints on the etiology, symptoms, and management of bipolar illness. In this thesis, psychological theories such as the behavioral activation/inhibition systems model, interpersonal interactions and social rhythm treatment approach, behavioral sensitization and kindling model, cognitive behavioral approach, and psychoanalytic approach are investigated. Bipolar disorder causes a broad variety of consequences. This condition has an impact on an individual's physical, mental, emotional, and social well-being. Bipolar illness may impair a person's self-esteem, motivation, focus, memory, decision-making skills, creativity, problem-solving abilities, and learning capacity. Bipolar disease may lead to failure, loss, loneliness, conflict, aggression, drug misuse, criminality, and suicide in a variety of settings, including job, school, family, friendship, and love. Bipolar illness may lower a person's quality of life and happiness. This thesis presents essential studies on the many areas of bipolar disorder.

Keywords : Bipolar Disorder, Psychological Theories, Domains

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ABBREVIATIONS / SYMBOLS

Yy	: Century
Vd	: And others
And Ark	: And his friends

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INTRODUCTION

Bipolar disorder is a chronic and recurring mental condition characterized by significant mood swings, mania, and depression. Bipolar illness is a widespread health issue globally, with a lifetime frequency ranging from 0.6 to 1.6% (Konuk et al., 2007). Bipolar disease has detrimental effects on patients' quality of life, functioning, social interactions, and adaptation. It also raises the chance of suicide (Köroğlu, 2013). Bipolar disorder is assumed to be caused by a combination of genetic, biochemical, psychological, and environmental variables (Kaleli, 2020).

Diagnostic System), an international diagnostic system, is used to diagnose and treat bipolar disorders. The Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders and the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) are utilized. The DSM and ICD classify bipolar disorder into several categories, provide diagnostic criteria for mania, hypomania, and depression, and describe subtypes of bipolar disorder. The DSM and ICD have updated their definitions and classifications of bipolar disorder throughout time. This thesis discusses the diagnosis and classification of bipolar disorder using DSM-5 (Çalışkan, 2007).

The treatment for bipolar disorder includes medication, psychotherapy, and psychosocial therapies. Although pharmacological therapy is beneficial in the acute and preventative treatment of bipolar illness, patients' adherence to medication may be poor, side effects may occur, and drug resistance may emerge. As a result, in the treatment of bipolar illness, psychotherapy and psychosocial therapies, in addition to pharmacological therapy, are becoming more important. Psychotherapy and psychosocial therapies seek to increase patients' awareness of the condition, stress management skills, social rhythms, mood control, and overall quality of life. This thesis will investigate psychological theories and therapeutic treatments connected to bipolar disorder (Hollander & Berlin, 2008).

Bipolar disorder is an illness that impacts many aspects of a patient's life. Bipolar disorder may have an impact on patients' personality features, cognitive abilities, sleep patterns, eating habits, sexual functions, physical health, social support, job and school performance, economic position, and legal issues. Determining the impact areas of bipolar disease is critical for recognizing patients' needs and issues, developing a treatment strategy and objectives, and

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assessing treatment success and outcomes. This thesis will cover the topics of bipolar disorder and associated studies (Merikangas et al., 2007).

Problem

Bipolar disorder refers to a bipolar mood condition. This condition causes the sufferer to oscillate between episodes of mania and depression. During the manic phase, the individual becomes very passionate, active, self-confident, and ambitious. During depression, the individual feels very unhappy, hopeless, useless, and weary. Bipolar illness may have a significant impact on a person's career, education, family, and social life.

The causes of bipolar disorder are not completely understood. Genetics, brain chemistry, stress, and trauma are suggested to be contributing factors. Bipolar disorder may be categorized into many categories. Bipolar I disorder affects patients who have at least one episode of mania and one episode of depression. Bipolar II disorder affects patients who have at least one episode of hypomania and one episode of sadness. Hypomania is a more moderate illness than mania. A psychiatrist conducts a clinical assessment to determine the diagnosis of bipolar illness.

Bipolar disorder is a curable illness. The treatment involves both medication and psychotherapy. Medication is used to help a person's mood, avoid attacks, and minimize negative effects. Psychotherapy enables the patient to deal with the sickness, express their feelings, enhance their relationships, and improve their quality of life. Psychological theories provide several views for explaining the etiology, symptoms, and management of bipolar illness. The behavioral activation/inhibition systems model investigates the association between personality factors and bipolar illness. The interpersonal interactions and social rhythm treatment method stresses how a person's everyday routines and social contacts, such as sleep, eating, and exercise, affect bipolar illness. The behavioral sensitization and ignition hypothesis contends that stressful situations and emotional responses cause bipolar disorder episodes. According to the cognitive behavioral method, a person's thoughts, emotions, and actions are all linked, and negative ideas exacerbate bipolar disease symptoms. According to the psychoanalytic method, early trauma and suppressed emotions contribute to the development of bipolar illness.

Bipolar disorder causes a broad variety of consequences. This condition has an impact on an individual's physical, mental, emotional, and social well-being. Bipolar illness may

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impair a person's self-esteem, motivation, focus, memory, decision-making skills, creativity, problem-solving abilities, and learning capacity. Bipolar disease may lead to failure, loss, loneliness, conflict, aggression, drug misuse, criminality, and suicide in a variety of settings, including job, school, family, friendship, and love. Bipolar illness may lower a person's quality of life and happiness.

If you want to perform research on bipolar illness, you must first establish the issue condition. The issue statement outlines the research's objective, significance, scope, constraints, and assumptions. The problem statement formulates the study topic or hypothesis. The issue scenario defines the study topic, methodology, data collecting and analysis tools, findings, and suggestions. The problem statement highlights the research's contribution, originality, dependability, and validity.

Bipolar illness is a mood disease that is widespread and has major implications. This condition causes the sufferer to go between bouts of mania and depression. During the manic phase, the individual becomes very passionate, active, self-confident, and ambitious. During depression, the individual feels very unhappy, hopeless, useless, and weary. Bipolar illness may have a significant impact on a person's career, education, family, and social life. Bipolar disorder is a curable illness. The treatment involves both medication and psychotherapy. Psychotherapy enables the patient to deal with the sickness, express their feelings, enhance their relationships, and improve their quality of life. Psychotherapy strategies include cognitive behavioral therapy, interpersonal and social rhythm treatment, family-focused therapy, and psychoeducation. Various research has validated the usefulness of these strategies. However, the effectiveness of these therapies on bipolar illness patients in Turkey has not been well studied. The purpose of this research is to compare the efficacy of psychotherapy approaches such as cognitive behavioral therapy, interpersonal and social rhythm treatment, family-focused therapy, and psychoeducation on bipolar illness patients in Turkey. This research seeks to improve the treatment of bipolar disorder patients, uncover the benefits and drawbacks of psychotherapy procedures, enhance the standards of psychotherapy practices, and add to the scientific literature in the area of psychotherapy.

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Aim

The purpose of this thesis is to provide current information on the diagnosis, treatment, and impact areas of bipolar disorder, to investigate psychological theories and psychotherapy approaches related to bipolar disorder, and to make recommendations for assessing and improving psychosocial functionality in bipolar disorder. This thesis is divided into five parts: introduction, first, second, third, and conclusion. The opening part explains the thesis's topic, goal, scope, and plan. The first section discusses the definition, history, classification, diagnostic criteria, epidemiology, etiology, clinical aspects, course, and outcome of bipolar disorder. In the second section, psychological theories and psychotherapy treatments to bipolar disorder are reviewed. The third segment covers the fields of bipolar disorder and associated studies. The conclusion part presents the thesis' results, assessments, limitations, and suggestions.

Importance

The significance of this study is to contribute to the treatment of bipolar disorder patients, compare the efficacy of psychotherapy approaches, enhance psychotherapy practice standards, and add to the scientific literature in the area of psychotherapy. Bipolar illness is a mood disease that is widespread and has major implications. This condition may have a detrimental impact on a person's job, education, family, and social life. Bipolar disorder is a curable illness. The treatment involves both medication and psychotherapy. Psychotherapy enables the patient to deal with the sickness, express their feelings, enhance their relationships, and improve their quality of life. Psychotherapy strategies include cognitive behavioral therapy, interpersonal and social rhythm treatment, family-focused therapy, and psychoeducation. Various research has validated the usefulness of these strategies. This study will disclose the benefits and drawbacks of psychotherapy procedures, improve psychotherapy practices, and add to the scientific literature in the area of psychotherapy. This study will help with the treatment of bipolar illness patients, assist the selection and use of psychotherapy approaches, and promote psychotherapy training and supervision. This study attempts to enhance the quality of life and happiness for bipolar illness patients.

FIRST PART

1. BIPOLAR DISORDER

1.1. Bipolar Disorder Definition

Bipolar disorder is a chronic, lifelong condition marked by recurring symptoms of mania, hypomania, and depression (Ceylan, 2001).

1.2. History of Bipolar Disorder

Depression has a lengthy history. Mania and depression are notions that have been known since ancient Greece and Rome. Homer is said to have used the Greek term "mani," indicating passion and rage, in the prelude to his epic Iliad in the seventh century BC. Hippocrates originally coined the word melancholy circa 450 AD. Hippocrates called this illness, which is now known as severe depression. He proposed that this disorder includes black bile, which indicates sleeplessness, loss of appetite, melancholy, anger, and helplessness (Sadock 2015).

Soranus hypothesized in the first century BC that ecstasy may be linked to sorrow. Aretaeus of Cappadocia characterized the relationship between mania and melancholia as intense mania experienced by the same patient at different times, with melancholy occurring before and during the mania (Akiskal, 2003).

In 1845, German psychiatrist Wilhelm Griesinger stressed the seasonal variation, stating that mania was more common in the spring and melancholia in the fall and winter. In addition, he described fast cycle mood disorders (Angst and Marneros 2001).

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Similarly, Falret proposes that the ailment recurs cyclically, and that some mental patients heal spontaneously while others do not. This difference has been dubbed "cyclic dementia." Bailarger described these individuals as having "double insanity." Later, in the 1870s, Kalbaum described psychosis as alternating bouts of despair and excitation. Mendel identified hypomania as the underlying cause of BP-II disease in 1881 (Tuna et al., 2012).

In 1896, German psychiatrist Emil Kraepelin characterized internal psychosis as "primary dementia and manic depression," claiming that manic-depressive sickness is cyclical. Kraepelin divided almost all major mood disorders into distinct groups from schizophrenia. This review included the similarity of the primary symptoms, the existence of a family history of the illness, and its prognostic aspects, which proceed with numerous exacerbations and remissions throughout life. However, it was noted that they did not result in severe deterioration. As a result, the notion of manic-depressive disorder was established to provide a more comprehensive view of the condition. Furthermore, he established the basis for today's "bipolar spectrum" by proposing that the condition manifests itself in a variety of ways, ranging from disposition to depression. Bleuler defined depressive and manic syndromes in the 1930s using criteria for evaluating affective disorders (Demir, 2021).

Karl Kleist conducted research to develop the notions of "unipolar and bipolar". Carl Leonard classified pictures with only depressed episodes as unipolar, images with both manic and depressive periods as bipolar, and images with only manic episodes as bipolar disorder. In the 1970s, considerable study was conducted on the taxonomy of psychopathology. All of these individuals were diagnosed with "affective disorder" (Leonhard, 2003).

It was believed that these investigations created the groundwork for bipolar disorder, which was included in the DSM classification in 1980. The absence of compelling clinical and neurobiological evidence to differentiate bipolar disorder from unipolar depression has encouraged researchers in this field to adopt the term bipolar spectrum. According to the DSM categorization system, the spectrum model depicts circumstances between major depressive disorder and bipolar disorder as an option for disturbed individuals who cannot be definitively identified (Tamayo et al., 2013).

The explanatory model classifies bipolar type II as fluctuating degrees of bipolar without natural breakpoints such as hypomania and serious disorder. Akiskal and Mallya adopt this technique in their chapter on interruptions that cannot be identified using the DSM setup (Akiskal and Mallaya, 1986).

The spectrum model is shown in Figure 1.1.

Unipolar Depression, Bipolar Disorders

Figure 1. Spectrum Model

Dunner et al. (1976) introduced the contemporary definition of bipolar disorder. In 1994, it was included to the DSM-IV as a discrete diagnosis (Köroğlu, 1994). The controversy about the pathological position of BP- II continues to this day. While some researchers regard BP-II to be a milder version of BP-I within the "bipolar spectrum," others believe it should be classed as a unique disorder from BP-1 (Akiskal and Pinto, 1999). According to the DSM-5, BP- II is not a moderate version of BP-1 (Harkavy - Friedman et al., 2006).

1.3. Bipolar Disorder Grouping

With the DSM-III categorization, the idea of pervasive affective disorder, which distinguishes bipolar disorder from severe depression, was validated. In 1987, the DSM-III-R category incorporated the concept of "depression." Because this idea relates to a persistent emotional state rather than only the present circumstance (Hollander and Berlin, 2008).

The 1994 DSM-IV classification of bipolar disorder is split into four categories: bipolar disorder I, bipolar disorder type II, cyclothymia, and bipolar disorder not otherwise specified. The DSM-IV does not include bipolar disorder except for antidepressant therapy for hypomanic/manic episodes or "substance-induced hypomanic/manic episodes." Meanwhile, several episodes and hypomanic states have been incorporated. The DSM-IV-TR classification, released in 2000, is based on the DSM-IV classification (Çalışkan, 2007).

has made significant advances in this area, recognizing bipolar illness type II as a separate diagnostic category. The inclusion of BP-II illness in the DSM-IV diagnostic group has resulted in an increase in the ratio of unipolar depression to bipolar disorder spectrum in favor of bipolar disorder (Kaleli, 2020).

In DSM-5, the term "mood disorder" was abolished, and the diagnostic criteria for "depressive disorder" and "bipolar and related disorders" were examined separately. The term "other psychiatric disorders" is no longer used in the DSM-IV-TR. According to Koroğlu (2013), clinical symptoms caused by a medical condition or drug use may be classified into subcategories.

1.4. Bipolar Disorder Diagnostic Criteria

When manic and hypomanic episodes occur, hypertension may be diagnosed. Type 1 bipolar is characterized by manic and depressed phases, and type 2 bipolar is characterized by hypomanic and depressive episodes. The DSM-5 has undergone several revisions, such as outlining the diagnostic criteria for these episodes and how bipolar is diagnosed, as well as recognizing depression as a distinguishing characteristic rather than categorizing mixed episodes as distinct episodes. The diagnostic criteria for major depressive episodes remained unchanged. Diagnostic criteria (A) and (B) for mania and hypomania improved, as did mood, goal-directed functioning, and internal strength, although duration criteria remained similar. Another significant change in DSM-5 is that manic/hypomanic symptoms are deemed appropriate to identify a manic/hypomanic episode if they occur during antidepressant therapy and continue to a symptomatic level beyond the physiological effects of treatment (Merikangas et al., 2007).

Bipolar disorder is grouped according to DSM 5 as follows (Konuk et al., 2007):

- *Bipolar Disorder I*
- *Bipolar Disorder II*
- *cyclothymia*
- *Substance/Drug-Induced Bipolar Disorder and Related Disorders*
- *Bipolar Disorder and Disorders Due to Other Medical Conditions*
- *Bipolar Disorder and Related Disorders, Other Unspecified Disorders*
- *Bipolar Disorder, Unspecified and Related Disorders*

1.4.1. Mania Period

Diagnostic criteria of the manic episode are shown in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Diagnostic Criteria for Mania Episode

Diagnostic Criteria	Descriptions
A.	includes an elevated, enthusiastic, or angry mood, as well as an amazing and continuous boost in goal-related activity and inner strength, that lasts at least seven days.
B.	<p>Three of the underlying symptoms are clearly present when a mood disorder occurs and there is an increase in inner strength or activity. These differ greatly from usual attitudes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having excessive self-esteem or delusions of grandeur, • Decreased need for sleep, • Talking more than ever, • Flight of ideas or the subjective experience of competing thoughts • Observation of interpretation or distraction, • Increases goal-directed activity or psychomotor stimulation, • Excessive involvement in activities that may lead to negative consequences.
C.	The mood illness is severe enough to significantly impede social or activity-related

	functioning, necessitating hospitalization to avert injury to the person, or exhibiting psychotic features.
D	This procedure cannot be explained by the physiological effects of a chemical or another medical condition.

Source: Öztekin et al., 2017

1.4.2. Hypomanic Period

Diagnostic criteria of the hypomanic episode are shown in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2. Diagnostic Criteria for Hypomanic Episode

Diagnostic Criteria	Descriptions
A.	A discrete period of time during which an unusual and persistent mood of effusiveness or irritability, as well as an extraordinary and sustained increase in goal-related activity and inner strength, occur for a considerable part of the day, virtually every day, for at least four consecutive days.
B.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the time of mood disturbance and heightened inner strength or activity, three of the underlying symptoms are present to an understandable extent. These are notably different from usual attitudes. • Inflated self-esteem or grandiose delusions. • End of sleep expense

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Talking more than usual• Thought views or subjective experiences that seem to compete with each other.• Reporting or observing distraction• It increases goal-directed activity or psychomotor stimulation.• Overloading on what can lead to negative consequences
C.	This period is described as a period in which an understandable change in functionality is experienced, which is very different from what is usual in periods when the individual is not symptomatic.
D	Others notice the mood disruption and the change in functioning.
TO	This time is not severe enough to significantly impair social or activity-related functioning or need hospitalization to avert damage to oneself or others. If psychotic symptoms appear, the time in question is referred to as a hypomanic phase.
F	This interval is incompatible with a substance's physiological effects.

Source: Yilmaz, 2019

1.4.3. Major Depression Era

the major depressive episode is shown in Table 1.3.

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Diagnostic Criteria	Descriptions
A.	<p data-bbox="810 347 1401 660">During the same two-week period, five of the underlying symptoms were present and there was a change in previous level of functioning. These symptoms include depressed mood, loss of interest, or lack of pleasure.</p> <ul data-bbox="858 694 1401 1960" style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="858 694 1401 784">• Self-reported or observed depression all day, almost every day<li data-bbox="858 806 1401 952">• A significant decrease in interest and pleasure in almost all activities for most of the day, almost every day,<li data-bbox="858 974 1401 1176">• Losing or gaining a lot of weight without trying to lose weight, or a decrease or increase in the desire to eat almost every day,<li data-bbox="858 1198 1401 1288">• Insomnia or oversleeping almost every day.<li data-bbox="858 1310 1401 1400">• Psychomotor taunting or slowness nearly every day<li data-bbox="858 1422 1401 1512">• Fatigue or lack of inner strength almost every day.<li data-bbox="858 1534 1401 1680">• Feelings of worthlessness, excessive or inappropriate guilt almost every day<li data-bbox="858 1702 1401 1792">• Trouble thinking, concentrating, or indecisiveness nearly every day<li data-bbox="858 1814 1401 1960">• Recurrent suicidal thoughts, recurring suicidal thoughts without planning specific actions.

B.	These symptoms may indicate a clinically severe difficulty or impairment in social, activity-related, or other critical areas of functioning.
C.	This period is not associated with the physiological effects of a substance or other health problem.

Source: Çelik and Hocaoğlu, 2016

1.4.4. Bipolar I Disorder

The diagnostic criteria of the Bipolar I Disorder period are listed as follows (Tuğlu and Şahin, 2010):

- Diagnostic criteria have been determined for at least one manic episode,
- mania and major depressive episodes cannot be more effectively explained by “*schizoaffective disorder, schizophrenia, schizophrenic disorder, delusional disorder, or other defined bipolar and related disorder*”.

1.4.5. Bipolar II Disorder

Diagnostic criteria of the Bipolar II Disorder period are shown in Table 1.4.

Diagnostic Criteria	Descriptions
A.	for at least one hypomanic episode and at least one major depressive episode has been met.
B.	There were no manic episodes at any time.
C.	hypomania and major depressive episodes cannot be more effectively expressed with “ <i>schizoaffective disorder, schizophrenia,</i>

	<i>schizophreniform disorder, delusional disorder, or other defined bipolar and related disorder ”.</i>
D	The unpredictability of depressive symptoms or frequent alternations between depressive and hypomanic episodes can lead to clinical depression and impairment in social, occupational, and other important activities.

Source: İbiloğlu and Çayköylü , 2011

1.5. Epidemiology of Bipolar Disorder

Various studies have shown that the lifetime prevalence of bipolar disorder ranges between 0.6 and 1.7%. However, due to challenges in the diagnostic procedure, these increases might be far higher. The newly developed notion of "bipolar spectrum" includes bipolar disorder type 1 and bipolar disorder type 2, which may be diagnosed as two-day hypomania, intermittent mania, intermittent short-term hypomania, drug cell-induced hypomania, and experimental trials (Ulutürk, 2020).

It is suggested that if bipolar disorder is considered a spectrum, the rate will not surpass 5% (Akiskal et al. 2000). In recent research, the lifetime prevalence of bipolar disorder type I was 1.0 percent; 1.1 percent for bipolar disorder type II; one-year prevalence is 0.6 percent for bipolar disorder type I; and 0.8 percent for bipolar disorder type II. The lifetime prevalence of subthreshold instances is 2.4%, whereas the one-year prevalence is 1.4% (Merikangas et al., 2007).

Clinical studies show that almost half of persons with bipolar disorder type II are first diagnosed with MDD (Ghaemi et al., 2002). It is reported that even if the disease's initial assault is hypomanic in character, these individuals are recognized for more than ten years (Angst, 2006). Furthermore, after being diagnosed with bipolar disorder type-II, only 5-7.5 percent of individuals suffer manic episodes in the long run, and their diagnosis changes to type-I (Coryell et al., 1995).

Much research has shown that the severity of bipolar illness is same in international and ethnic settings. It has been proven that the prevalence of bipolar disorder type I does not vary by gender. Female patients have more severe depression, whereas male patients experience more severe manic episodes. The incidence of BP type II in men and women is reported to be 1:1.5 (Angst et al., 2003).

According to the World Health Organization, bipolar illness is the sixth most common condition causing loss of ability in society. At the same time, the fact that the majority of persons with bipolar disease are young and middle-aged, which constitutes the society's labor, increases the economic cost imposed by bipolar disorder (Akkaya et al., 2012).

1.6. Etiology of Bipolar Disorder

From the past to the present, research has been performed to establish the etiology of bipolar illness, but the particular cause has yet to be identified. Sadock (2015) listed some of the elements thought to be responsible for the disease's development.

Family, twin, and adoption studies show the importance of genetic load in bipolar illness. According to Smoller and Finn (2003), the frequency of bipolar disorder among first-degree relatives of patients with bipolar disorder ranges from 3 to 8%, whereas the prevalence of unipolar depressive illness is 14.8%.

The risk of developing bipolar disorder in relatives of people with bipolar disorder is higher than that of unipolar depressive disorder in the general population; the most common mood disorder in relatives of people with bipolar disorder is unipolar depressive disorder (Sullivan et al., 2000).

Twin studies contain more co-morbidity data in identical twins than fraternal twins. Various studies have revealed that comorbidity rates among identical twin wives of bipolar illness patients range from 45 to 75 percent (Craddock and Jones, 2001).

It is reported that research done on people with the same genetic traits, such as identical twins, reveal a range of phenotypes associated with bipolar illness susceptibility genes. Öztürk (2008) suggests that environmental variables, in addition to genetics, play a significant part in the development of the illness, since concordance is not always 100% among identical twins.

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Large family investigations have shown that bipolar illness types I and II share many inherited traits, although they also vary in inheritance. According to a genome dense linkage study, bipolar disorder type II is associated with the "18q21 and 9p33 chromosome regions," as opposed to bipolar disorder type I (Nwulia et al., 2007). Another research discovered that dysbindin gene variation was more related with bipolar illness type I than type II (Joo et al., 2007).

Progranulin gene substitution is helpful in lowering the likelihood of bipolar disorder type I but has no impact on type II. These findings provide credence to the notion that bipolar disorder types I and II have comparable illness subgroups (Galimberti et al., 2014).

The discovery that pharmacological drugs are effective in the treatment of depression has fueled biochemical study. So yet, no well-defined biochemical abnormality has been found. Pathophysiological hypotheses have mostly centered on norepinephrine, serotonin, and dopamine (Sadock, 2015).

Mania is assumed to be connected with monoamine elevation, while monoamine depression is linked to depression. Bipolar disorder is associated with higher levels of 3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenylglycol, a noradrenaline metabolite (Berns and Nemeroff, 2003).

Lithium medication, which is successful in both treatment and prevention, dramatically reduces MHPG in CSF and noradrenaline levels in urine, and this decline is more apparent in individuals who respond to lithium than in those who do not. It has been shown that alterations in the noradrenergic system discovered during postmortem brain investigations are connected to G-protein modifications (Vidin, 2019).

Serotonergic activity is thought to be diminished in depression owing to low levels of 5-hydroxy-indole-acetic acid (5-OHIAA), a key serotonin breakdown product, in the cerebrospinal fluid. Serotonin helps to regulate sleep, wakefulness, hunger, sexual desire, and body temperature. High amounts of L-tryptophan, a precursor of serotonin, may create a manic state (Sobczak et al., 2002).

During mania, the dopamine system becomes more active. Tuna et al. (2012) feel that this activity contributes to depression. Manic episodes may be caused by drugs that enhance dopamine levels, such as L-Dopa, bromocriptine, and amphetamine. Dopamine receptor blockers, such as antipsychotics It contains antimanic properties and may induce depressed

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symptoms such as anhedonia, somnolence, and weariness. As a result, dopamine activity is considered a predictor of psychomotor activity (Demir, 2021).

Another neurotransmitter implicated in the pathophysiology of bipolar illness that has lately been explored is glutamate. In bipolar disorder, glutamate levels rise in the occipital cortex but fall in the prefrontal cortex. Ketamine, which controls glutamate, has antidepressant properties. Clinical trials have also shown that ketamine infusions alleviate suicidal thoughts (Machado-Vieira et al., 2012).

Second messengers are believed to have an increasingly important part in the pathophysiology of bipolar illness. The intracellular second messenger's cyclic adenosine monophosphate and phosphoinositol stimulate biological amine levels via a signaling cascade mechanism. G proteins mediate the actions of norepinephrine, serotonin, dopamine, and acetylcholine. These systems' products influence the gene expression of enzymes, receptors, and carrier proteins involved in neural function. The effects of mood stabilizers on second messenger systems serve as the foundation for hypotheses on the pathophysiology of bipolar illness.

Suppresses the production of cyclic adenosine monophosphate by decreasing the Gα-GTP link, which is required for G protein activation. Recent signal transduction investigations have demonstrated that glycogen synthase kinase-3 activity is elevated in bipolar disorder, whereas lithium decreases this activity by directly blocking GSK-3. GSK-3 is regarded as a key enzyme in the nervous system, influencing "neuronal function, neurogenesis, synaptic plasticity, neuronal cell death and survival, and gene expression." GSK-3's inhibitory regulatory function may be compromised in various bipolar disorder pathways (Avissar et al., 1988).

Excess dopamine activity at dopamine D2 receptors in bipolar disease causes signals to activate GSK-3 during mania. However, serotonin or BDNF deficit lowers GSK-3 inhibitory signaling while increasing GSK-3 activity. This suggests that lithium is beneficial for depressive and manic illnesses (Jope, 2011).

Changes in the neuroendocrine system are thought to have a significant part in the disease's pathogenesis. Bipolar disorder primarily affects the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis. Increased activity of the HPA axis is seen as a biological sign of illness. The hypothalamic paraventricular nucleus releases CRF, which increases the pituitary glands systemic production of ACTH. The adrenal glands respond by secreting cortisol (Turan and Lushi, 2014).

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CSF cortisol and urine free cortisol levels are higher during the mixed stages of bipolar disorder. These alterations are also seen in depression. Although the dexamethasone suppression test produces unsatisfactory results in individuals with unipolar depression, its practical use is restricted. The CR induction test remains therapeutically relevant. ACTH responses to exogenous CRF are reduced in depression, but not in mania or control. When dexamethasone is used with a CRF stimulation test, cortisol levels rise in depressive patients compared to controls and unipolar depressed patients. This shows that bipolar depression is a distinct clinical condition from unipolar depression (Pariante and Miller 2001).

The hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis has been identified as another topic of neuroendocrine system study. Depression is associated with decreased thyroid stimulating hormone response and elevated plasma thyroxine levels (Öztürk and Uluşahin, 2008). Several investigations have shown increased CSF thyroid-stimulating hormone levels in depressed individuals (Banki et al., 1988).

MRI investigations have shown volume alterations and ventricular dilatation in several parts of the brain (Hallahan et al., 2011). A meta-analysis indicated that people with bipolar illness had increased lateral and third ventricle volume and reduced corpus callosum area, regardless of disease duration (Kempton et al., 2008).

Studies on the link between bipolar illness and white and gray matter lesions reveal structural brain abnormalities. The extensive frontotemporal white matter lesions seen in bipolar disorder are thought to be linked to the disease's cognitive symptoms. Bipolar illness is linked with high-density lesions in the deep white matter, cortical gray matter, frontal and parietal lobes, which vary regardless of age, disease start, or lithium medication. However, there is an association between lithium consumption and gray matter (Vita et al., 2009).

Abnormal white matter promotes delayed myelination without axonal loss, which has been linked to bipolar illness (Benedetti et al., 2011). White matter abnormalities might be a sign of bipolar illness (van Baal et al., 2012). Gray matter has become a major concept, making the condition less prevalent (Bora and Pantelis, 2011).

Functional neuroimaging investigations have shown that bipolar depressive individuals had poorer cortical metabolism than controls or unipolar depressed patients. Bipolar disorder is characterized by a decrease in right prefrontal cortex activity, which can cause symptoms such

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as impaired impulse control, risk-taking, distraction, difficulty concentrating, and patient confusion, similar to manic symptoms (Berns and Nemeroff, 2003).

During executive function, positron emission tomography investigations on individuals with bipolar I disorder revealed reduced glucose uptake in the bilateral frontal ganglia, insula, striatum, and prefrontal cortex while increasing glucose absorption in the left hippocampus. Both subtypes have frontal impairment affecting executive skills. However, it has been shown to be milder in bipolar II illness (Li et al., 2012).

Environmental factors are assumed to have a significant impact in the development and duration of depression (Akiskal, 2003). A significant incident often worsens the first bout of depression. However, the majority of these incidents are not typical. However, it should be remembered that these occurrences will not affect everyone. Öztürk and Uluşahin (2008) suggest that biological and psychological predispositions have a significant influence in illness development. Although triggering events have a definite impact on early sickness experiences, the same cannot be stated for later illnesses. According to longitudinal research, roughly 13% of episodic patients reported a traumatic life event in the six months before illness start (Angst, 1986).

Affective temperament traits are linked to the etiology, phenomenology, and therapy of bipolar illness. Familial load, early start, high incidence of recurrence, and a predisposition to manic shift under the effect of antidepressants have all been proposed as factors in the association between affective temperament and bipolar illness (89-91).

Recent years have seen an increase in study on the antecedents of bipolar illness. Akiskal (1986) proposed that mood temperaments cause depression and identified five major temperaments. The primary temperaments are outlined below:

- *Melancholia,*
- *Extreme Mood,*
- *cyclothymia ,*
- *Irritability,*
- *Anxiety*

Bipolar disorder is connected with bulimic and cyclothymic temperament, while unipolar depression is associated with depression (Hecht et al., 1997). Emotional impulsive

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traits are linked to the etiology, symptoms, and treatment of bipolar illness. The following features have been suggested to explain the association between emotional temperament and bipolar disorder (Brieger et al., 2003).

- *Family Tension,*
- *Early Start,*
- *High Relapse Rates,*
- *Proneness To Manic Transformation Under the Influence of Antidepressants*

The "Temperament and Character Inventory" was assessed using four subscales: thrill of discovery, impulsivity, extravagance, and disorder (92).

Cloninger is unquestionably one of the most prolific writers on temperament and character. Cloninger created a dimensional psychological model of personality that explains normal and pathological differences in temperament and personality, which are regarded as the two primary components of personality. He added three personality dimensions to the original four personality dimension model to develop the "Temperament and Personality Inventory" scale (Cloninger et al. 1993).

" *Temperament and Personality Inventory* " are stated as follows (Cloninger et al., 1993):

- *Harm Avoidance,*
- *Quest for Innovation,*
- *Reward Addiction,*
- *Persistence*

Novelty seekers are prone to impulsive conduct, get quickly irritated when under pressure, and disregard laws and regulations if they felt it would provide them pleasure and excitement. People who are uninterested in innovation will continue to follow the status quo. The hunt for innovation in the "Temperament and Personality Inventory" has evolved at many scales. These scales are: (Cloninger et al., 1993).

- *Self-Discovery Motivation,*
- *Enthusiasm,*

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- *Splurge,*
- *Confusion.*

Patients with bipolar illness, patients with unipolar depression, and healthy controls all have greater novelty-seeking values and lower stability values (Osher et al., 1999). In the long run, high novelty seeking values may become a sign of dysfunction.

Low self-control and a lack of commitment to the reward of personality transformation establish the conditions for suicide. When confronted with life events or pressures such as sadness, people tend to give up on themselves (Ak et al., 2008).

Bipolar illness research has focused on two kinds of personality structures. The qualities of the first and second personality structures are stated below (Savitz and Ramesar, 2006):

First Personality Structure:

- *Anger,*
- *Anxiety,*
- *Depression,*
- *Guilt,*
- *Proneness to Other Negative Emotions and Cognitions*

Second Personality Structure:

- *New Perspectives,*
- *exclusion,*
- *non-blocking*
- *Changeable Emotions*

" *Mourning and Melancholy* ", Freud underlined the parallels between depression and grieving symptoms, comparing the two disorders. Depression produces a loss of self-esteem, the sensation that "I lost my loved ones, I am not loved, I am bad anymore," and actual or perceived losses. According to Öztürk and Uluşahin (2008), those who are left behind do not feel undervalued.

From a psychoanalytic perspective, the unconscious reasons and processes of depression may be stated as follows: The human superego is rigorous and unforgiving, indecision reigns

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supreme in relationships, and a contradiction seems to internalize the object of affection. While love and hate coexist, hatred is unconscious. There is often a feeling of personal loss as a result of current circumstances or a shift in mentality. This sense of loss generates subliminal wrath, bitterness, love, and desire. In a powerful superego, anger and contempt are aimed at the person, self-confidence declines, and the individual perceives himself as worthless, insignificant, and sinful. Furthermore, life lacks significance for him, and he must die. This circumstance causes a mental collapse (Öztürk and Uluşahin, 2008).

Manic episodes have been described psychoanalytically as a defense against despair and a release of control from the too punitive superego. Abraham struggles against the too strict and authoritarian superego, which creates despair. According to him, restrictions and regulations do not apply in the life of a manic patient. A manic patient's life becomes one in which individuals may do anything they want (Tuna et al., 2012).

1.7. Clinical Features, Course and Outcome in Bipolar Disorder

Bipolar illness often starts in the early twenties, and depression takes an average of 5 to 6 years to return. The median age of onset for bipolar disorder 1 is 18 years, whereas bipolar disorder 2 is 22 years (Merikangas et al., 2007).

Many studies have linked the disease's early beginning to a bad prognosis. Comorbidity of alcohol and drug use disorders has been shown to be more frequent in early-onset bipolar disorder than in individuals without early onset. According to Perlis et al. (2004), the comorbidity of panic disorder with agoraphobia is greater in instances of early onset.

Furthermore, several studies have shown that mixed phase, psychotic symptoms, psychosis, suicidal ideation, fast cycling, delayed treatment, dysfunction, and persistent symptoms are more common in early phases. If the illness develops beyond the age of 60, additional conditions such as neurological, infectious, or inflammatory disorders should be explored (Shulman and Herrmann, 1999).

The chance of recurrence of bipolar disorder is high. According to reports, 40 to 50% of patients have a second manic episode within two years following their first. The majority of individuals suffer depressed episodes, whereas 10 to 20% solely have manic periods. Bipolar illness often starts with depression and is more frequent in women. A manic episode often starts rapidly but evolves slowly, sometimes taking 1 to 2 weeks (Begley et al., 2001).

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Untreated mania lasts around three months and seldom becomes chronic. Depressive episodes often start later than mania, and untreated depression may continue 6 to 13 months. The therapy takes around three months. If antidepressant therapy is discontinued before three months, symptoms commonly return (Tuna et al., 2012). Days with depressed symptoms are three times more common in bipolar 1 patient than days with hypomanic/manic symptoms, and forty times more frequent in bipolar 2 patients (Pirinçi, 2012).

Depression occurs more often in bipolar II individuals. As a result, it is determined that people with type 2 bipolar disease have a longer duration of depression than those with bipolar type 1. As a result, the prognosis for people with bipolar II disease is poor in terms of functional impairment during depression (Mantere et al., 2008). Subtypes with atypical depression symptoms have been shown to be more frequent in bipolar II disorder than in bipolar I illness. In the same research, the bipolar I group had higher levels of depressive and psychotic symptom categories.

It has been reported that a seasonal course is more typical in people with type 2 bipolar illness. While the ratio of manic to depressive episodes stays constant in most men as the illness advances, in women, this ratio shifts toward depressive episodes with time. Women had greater rates of fast cycling, drug-induced manic conversion, suicide attempts, and late onset than males (Benazzi, 2003).

The average lifetime suicide attempt rate in bipolar illness is 30%. Twenty percent of the suicide attempts are deadly. Guilt and suicide thoughts are more prevalent in type 2 depression than in type 1, and they persist between bouts of rumination depression. However, there was no difference in suicide attempts or feelings of despair among individuals with bipolar disorder I and II depression (Valtonen et al., 2008).

The prognosis for bipolar disorder is outlined below: The manic episode continues, the patient and his family are eligible for therapy, and the recovery time is lengthy. Family and work environments are regarded as favorable. Negative trend indicators (Öztürk and Uluşahin, 2008):

- *Early Start,*
- *Permanent Presence of Temporary Manic and Depressive Symptoms,*
- *Other Comorbid Psychiatric Disorders,*

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- *Mixed Periods,*
- *Quick Loop,*
- *Presence of Alcohol or substance use disorders.*

SECOND PART

2. PSYCHOLOGICAL THEORIES ABOUT BIPOLAR DISORDER

2.1. Behavioral Activation/Inhibition Systems Model

The Behavioral Activation/Inhibition Systems Model is a personality model based on Reinforcement Sensitivity Theory by Gray (1987, 1990). According to this paradigm, people's conduct is influenced by two fundamental motivational systems that respond to reward and punishment signals. The systems are:

- *The Behavioral Inhibition System (BIS) is a punishment perception system that causes unpleasant feelings and actions including dread, anxiety, and avoidance. When a person receives cues of danger or threat, BIS inhibits or pauses their actions. BIS is linked to psychopathologies such as anxiety disorders, depression, and obsessive-compulsive disorder.*
- *The Behavioral Activation System (BAS) promotes good feelings and behaviors, including enjoyment, excitement, and attachment. When the BAS detects reward or incentive signals, it activates or begins the individual's behavior. BAS is linked to personality characteristics and psychopathologies such as sensation seeking, impulsivity, and mania.*

The BIS/BAS Scale, established by Carver and White (1994), is the most widely used instrument for assessing these two systems. This scale has four subscales: behavioral inhibition, fun seeking, reward sensitivity, and impulse. Şişman (2012) studied the validity and reliability of this scale after adapting it to Turkish.

Behavioral Inhibition/Activation Systems Model: A Theory of Personality

Personality is an area of psychology that seeks to explain the similarities and contrasts between people's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. Personality theories help us understand how personality characteristics develop, are assessed, and interpreted. One of these hypotheses is the Behavioral Inhibition/Activation Systems Model. This model is based on Gray's (1987, 1990) Reinforcement Sensitivity Theory. According to this idea, people's conduct is influenced

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by two fundamental motivational systems that respond to reward and punishment signals. These mechanisms are known as Behavioral Inhibition System (DIS) and Behavioral Activation System (DAS).

Behavioral Inhibition/Activation Systems Model

Gray's (1987, 1990) Reinforcement Sensitivity Theory aims to explain how reward and punishment signals influence people's behavior. According to this hypothesis, the human brain has two primary motivational systems: the Behavioral Inhibition System (DIS) and the Behavioral Activation System (DAS). These systems regulate people's emotional and behavioral reactions.

DIS is a punishment perception system that generates unpleasant feelings and actions including dread, anxiety, and avoidance. When a person receives cues of danger or threat, DIS inhibits or pauses their actions. DIS is linked to psychopathologies such anxiety disorders, depression, and obsessive-compulsive disorder (Bijttebier et al., 2009).

DAS is a reward perception system that triggers good feelings and actions including enjoyment, excitement, and attachment. When the DAS detects reward or incentive signals, it activates or begins the individual's behavior. DAS is linked to personality characteristics and psychopathologies such sensation seeking, impulsiveness, and mania (Bijttebier et al., 2009).

Individuals' personality traits are determined by two primary factors: DIS and DAS. DIS and DAS assist us forecast how people will behave emotionally, cognitively, and behaviorally in certain circumstances. For example, a person with a high DIS score may feel apprehensive and bashful in a new or unpleasant environment. A person with a high DAS score may be both excited and fearless in the same scenario.

Behavioral Inhibition/Activation Systems Scale

Carver and White (1994) established the DIS/DAS Scale, which is the most widely used instrument for measuring DIS and DAS systems. This scale consists of 24 items divided

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into four subscales: behavioral inhibition, fun seeking, reward sensitivity, and impulse. These subscales capture various characteristics of the DIS and DAS systems.

The Behavioral Inhibition subscale is an overall indication of the DIS system. This subscale assesses the individual's dread, anxiety, and avoidance response to punishment or threat signals. Statements on this subscale include "I am afraid of making mistakes" and "I worry a lot if something goes wrong."

The Fun Seeking subscale assesses the desire for new and interesting experiences, which is one part of the DAS system. This subscale assesses the individual's propensity to shun dull and ordinary circumstances in favor of more exciting and adventurous ones. Items on this subscale include comments like "I enjoy doing new and different things" and "I get bored when I have to do something boring."

The Reward Sensitivity subscale assesses excitement and proclivity to respond to reward or incentive cues, which is another part of the DAS system. This subscale assesses an individual's drive for good outcomes such as achievement, recognition, and affection. This subscale has items like "I feel very happy when I am successful" and "Being with people I love makes me very excited."

The Impulse subscale assesses impulsive and unplanned behavior, which is another part of the DAS system. This subscale assesses the individual's tendency to act without contemplating the consequences and difficulties regulating oneself. Statements on this subscale include "When I want to do something, I do it immediately" and "I have difficulty restraining myself."

The DIS/DAS measure is a five-point Likert-type measure. Each item has one of two options: "Strongly disagree" (1) or "Strongly agree" (5). The scale is scored by adding the elements from each subscale. Şişman (2012) performed validity and reliability studies on the Turkish scale. According to Şişman (2012), the Turkish version of the scale is largely consistent with the original and retains its four-factor structure. In addition, the scale's internal consistency and test-retest reliability coefficients were found to be satisfactory.

the Behavioral Inhibition/Activation Systems Model in Psychological Research

- *The DIS/DAS paradigm has been used to several fields of psychological study. This paradigm offers a framework for understanding how people express their emotional, cognitive, and behavioral reactions in various contexts. This model is employed in many study fields, including:*
- *The DIS/DAS model explains how motivational systems influence the development and progression of psychopathological diseases. For example, Bijttebier et al. (2009) investigated the relationship between the DIS and DAS systems and several illnesses, including eating disorders, drug misuse, bipolar disorder, and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. This research discovered a relationship between the DIS and DAS systems and disorder symptoms, causes, and therapies.*
- *The DIS/DAS model is used to analyze emotional and behavioral responses in interpersonal interactions. Gable, Reis, and Elliot (2000) studied how the DIS and DAS systems impact people' reactions to their partners' performance in romantic relationships. Individuals with a high DAS system reacted positively and supportively to their partners' accomplishment, but those with a strong DIS system reacted negatively and jealously.*
- *The DIS/DAS paradigm explains motivation, performance, and success in learning and education. Şişman (2012) investigated how DIS and DAS systems impact students' academic accomplishment, self-efficacy, and learning styles. In this research, it was shown that students with a high DAS system had more academic performance, self-efficacy, and active learning style than students with a high DIS system.*

2.2. Interpersonal Relationships and Social Rhythm Therapy Approach

It is a psychotherapy technique for the treatment of bipolar illness. This strategy seeks to help the patient realize and manage the association between interruptions in social rhythm and the start of previous episodes of mental disease. This strategy employs psychoeducational and behavioral strategies to preserve social rhythms and sleep/wakefulness cycles. This strategy is closely connected to the "social zeitgeber theory," which highlights that the social rhythm pattern influences circadian rhythm synchronization in those with or at risk of bipolar spectrum

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disorders. This technique has been found to improve the course of bipolar disorder (Frank et al., 2008).

Bipolar disorder is a mental condition marked by significant mood swings and periods of mania and sadness. Bipolar disorder is a severe condition that impairs quality of life, functioning, and relationships, has a high recurrence rate, and increases the risk of suicide. Although medication is necessary in the treatment of bipolar illness, it is not adequate in itself. In addition to medicine, psychotherapy may be used to treat bipolar disorder. Psychotherapy teaches patients about the condition, attack symptoms, triggers, and coping strategies, as well as how to develop their social support network and improve their quality of life. Interpersonal interactions and social rhythm treatment is one of the psychotherapy strategies used (Frank et al., 2008).

Frank et al. established the Interpersonal Relations and Social Rhythm Therapy Approach. This strategy seeks to help the patient realize and manage the association between interruptions in social rhythm and the start of previous episodes of mental disease. This strategy employs psychoeducational and behavioral strategies to preserve social rhythms and sleep/wakefulness cycles (Miklovitz & Scott, 2009). This strategy is closely connected to the "social zeitgeber theory," which highlights that the social rhythm pattern influences circadian rhythm synchronization in those with or at risk of bipolar spectrum disorders. According to this hypothesis, social rhythms are external signals that regulate an individual's biological clock. abnormalities in social rhythms may cause abnormalities in the biological clock and mood attacks. As a result, regular and consistent social rhythms are essential in the treatment of bipolar disease (Frank et al. 2000).

The goal of this section of the study is to introduce the interpersonal relations and social rhythm therapy approach in bipolar disorder, explain the steps involved in applying this approach, provide information about its effectiveness, and provide some examples of how it is used in psychological research.

Interpersonal Relationships and Social Rhythm Therapy Approach

The interpersonal interactions and social rhythm therapy approach is a psychotherapy technique used to treat bipolar illness. This strategy seeks to help the patient realize and manage the association between interruptions in social rhythm and the start of previous episodes of mental disease. This strategy employs psychoeducational and behavioral strategies to preserve social rhythms and sleep/wakefulness cycles.

Psychoeducation teaches the patient about his condition, signs of attacks, triggers, and coping strategies. Psychoeducation improves patients' acceptance of the condition, adherence to therapy, and quality of life. Psychoeducation may be provided to patients individually or in groups. Psychoeducation informs patients on the diagnosis, symptoms, causes, therapy, complications, prevention, and management of bipolar illness. In addition, the patient is given training and guidance on topics such as the importance of social rhythms, keeping a social rhythm diary, avoiding disrupting factors, maintaining sleep / wakefulness patterns, stress management, emotion recognition and expression, problem solving, communication skills, and strengthening the social support network (Özdel and Ekinici, 2011).

Behavioral approaches assist patients in maintaining and improving their social rhythms as well as their sleep/wake cycles. Behavioral techniques assist the patient in planning their daily activities, keeping a social rhythm diary, avoiding factors that disrupt social rhythms, practicing sleep hygiene, maintaining sleep / wakefulness patterns, dealing with stress, recognizing and expressing emotions, solving problems, improving communication skills, and establishing a social support network. This involves empowerment (Özdel and Ekinici, 2011). Behavioral approaches assist the patient to reach the objectives that he and his psychotherapist have established. The psychotherapist might use behavioral approaches on an individual or group basis.

2.3. Behavioral Sensitization and Ignition Model

The behavioral sensitization and kindling model are a theoretical framework for explaining the variables that impact people's usage of health care. This model was created by Andersen (1968) and then refined by several academics. The model classifies healthcare usage

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into three categories: person characteristics, health behaviors, and healthcare system characteristics. Individual characteristics include demographic, socioeconomic, and health status-related aspects that influence an individual's likelihood and need for health care. Individual characteristics include age, gender, income, education, insurance status, and the existence of a chronic condition. These variables influence an individual's access to and demand for health care (Andersen, 1968).

Health behaviors include attitudes, beliefs, values, and practices that impact how people utilize health care. Health habits include things like health knowledge, health literacy, a healthy lifestyle, trust in health services, and satisfaction with health services. These variables impact a person's attitude and preferences regarding healthcare.

Health system characteristics include elements that influence health care delivery and quality. Cost, accessibility, variety, organization, regulation, and monitoring of health services are all examples of health system features. These variables influence the availability and quality of health care.

The model also depicts the connections among these three components. Individual qualities, for example, may have an impact on health behavior. Health habits may have an impact on how the health-care system functions. Individual qualities may be influenced by aspects of the health system. The model stresses the complexity and dynamic nature of healthcare utilization. The approach may also be used to assess the equity of healthcare consumption. Equity entails delivering health treatments based on need. The approach seeks to assess if there are discrepancies in health care usage based on person characteristics, health habits, and health-system features. Inequalities diminish the equity of healthcare use. The model may inform policy suggestions to promote equitable access to health care (Kılıç and Çalışkan, 2013).

2.4. Cognitive Behavioral Approach

The cognitive behavioral method is a psychological approach that assumes that an individual's emotions, ideas, and actions interact with one another, and that this interaction influences the individual's quality of life. This approach contends that the individual's

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perception and interpretation of reality, rather than actual reality, is the basis of the issues he or she is experiencing. As a result, it seeks to transform the individual's negative, illogical, and dysfunctional thinking patterns into more positive, logical, and functional ones.

The cognitive behavioral approach combines cognitive and behavioral treatment approaches. Cognitive therapy assists the client in identifying and questioning their ideas, as well as developing alternate thoughts. Behavioral therapy assists the person in learning new behaviors, avoiding bad habits, and reinforcing favorable ones. This improves the individual's cognitive and behavioral abilities. The cognitive behavioral method has been shown to be useful in the treatment of a variety of psychological diseases and issues. A cognitive behavioral approach may be used to treat depression, anxiety, obsessive-compulsive disorder, panic disorder, phobias, eating disorders, drug abuse, sleep disorders, personality disorders, and relationship issues.

2.5. Psychoanalytic Approach

The psychoanalytic method, created by Sigmund Freud, seeks to understand human personality, behavior, and psychological disorders. According to Freud (2010), the majority of human psychological processes are unconscious and have an impact on human emotions, ideas, and actions.

The psychoanalytic method posits that the human psyche is made up of three structures: id, ego, and superego. The id is the component of the mind that embodies natural, primal drives like sexuality and violence. The id operates on the pleasure principle, seeking to satisfy its inclinations. The superego is the component of the mind responsible for representing societal norms, values, and morality. The superego follows the ideal principle and strives to repress impulses. The ego is the component of the mind that strives to reconcile the conflict between the id and the superego and behave in accordance with reality. The ego functions on the reality principle, ensuring that inclinations are postponed or adequately gratified (Freud, 2010). According to the psychoanalytic viewpoint, human psychological issues stem from unconscious conflicts, suppressed emotions, traumatic memories, and early experiences. As a result, the psychoanalytic approach's therapy goal is to disclose and increase awareness of the individual's unconscious processes.

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The psychoanalytic approach employs a therapeutic technique known as psychoanalysis. Psychoanalysis is predicated on the person expressing his or her unconscious processes using methods such as free association, dream analysis, resistance, transference, and interpretation, while the therapist analyzes these processes. Psychoanalysis is a prolonged and thorough therapeutic procedure (Freud, 2010).

The psychoanalytic method has contributed much to our knowledge of human psychology. However, this technique is not without criticism. For example, critics have said that the psychoanalytic method is unscientific, untestable, and unverifiable, sexist, and culturally prejudiced, and that the therapeutic process is excessively lengthy and costly.

THIRD PART

3. AREAS OF AFFECT OF BIPOLAR DISORDER

Bipolar disorder is a mental condition in which a person's mood fluctuates dramatically, alternating between episodes of mania and depression. Bipolar illness may have a significant influence on one's quality of life, functioning, relationships, and overall health. Bipolar illness is a complicated condition caused by a mix of genetic, biochemical, and environmental variables. Bipolar illness may be managed and treated with the proper therapy and support.

Below is a broad assessment of bipolar disorder and its areas of effect.

Intolerance of Uncertainty: People diagnosed with bipolar illness may exhibit a psychological feature known as intolerance of uncertainty. Intolerance of uncertainty is characterized as being afraid that an unknown event or circumstance may have undesirable effects, being unable to tolerate uncertainty, and going to extreme lengths to remove ambiguity. Intolerance to ambiguity is linked to anxiety, despair, stress, bad quality of life, and suicide risk in bipolar illness (Öztürk & Uluşahin, 2008).

People with bipolar disorder may be unable to tolerate uncertainty since the illness's course, the timing and intensity of episodes, treatment response, and future expectations are all unknown. Because bipolar disorder is a chronic and recurring condition, patients find it impossible to forecast when and what kind of attack they will have, how long the treatment will continue and how successful it will be, and what complications the sickness will bring for them and their loved ones. This ambiguity may lead patients to feel uncontrollable, powerless, and helpless, to experience worry, dread, and despair about the future, to elevate stress levels, to worsen depressive symptoms, and to consider suicide (Gangon et al., 1998).

Yıldız et al. (2013) found that psychotherapy approaches such cognitive behavioral therapy, acceptance and attachment therapy, mindfulness, and meditation may effectively treat bipolar disorder. These strategies may help patients perceive uncertainty more positively, learn to accept and manage with uncertainty, become more flexible and adaptive to uncertainty,

decrease anxiety, depression, and stress symptoms, and improve their overall quality of life and well-being. (Şen and Yıldız, 2013).

Bipolar Disorder and Attachment

Attachment is the emotional bond formed with caregivers in childhood . Attachment affects the way of relating in adulthood, the sense of trust, the need for closeness, and the ability to cope with separation . People with bipolar disorder often have insecure attachment styles . Insecure attachment is associated with more severe symptoms, more frequent episodes, poorer functioning, more relationship problems, and a higher risk of suicide in bipolar disorder . Attachment styles are difficult to change, but skills for secure attachment can be improved with psychotherapy. (Şen and Yıldız, 2013).

Bipolar Disorder and Suicide

Bipolar disorder is a mental condition characterized by significant mood swings that oscillate between mania and sadness. Bipolar illness has a detrimental influence on a person's quality of life, functioning, relationships, and health. Bipolar illness is a complicated condition caused by a mix of genetic, biochemical, and environmental influences. Bipolar illness may be managed and treated with the right therapy and support.

The following is a broad assessment of bipolar disorder and its areas of effect.

Intolerance of Uncertainty: Individuals with bipolar illness may exhibit a psychological feature known as intolerance of uncertainty. Intolerance of uncertainty may be characterized as being afraid that an unknown event or circumstance will have undesirable effects, being unable to tolerate uncertainty, and going to extreme lengths to eradicate ambiguity. Intolerance of ambiguity has been linked to anxiety, despair, stress, bad quality of life, and suicide risk in bipolar illness (Öztürk & Uluşahin, 2008).

People suffering with bipolar disorder may be unable to tolerate uncertainty since the duration of the disease, the timing and intensity of episodes, treatment response, and future expectations are all unknown. Because bipolar disorder is a chronic and recurring condition,

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sufferers find it impossible to anticipate when and what kind of attack they will have, how long and how successful the treatment will be, and what complications the sickness will bring for themselves and their loved ones. This ambiguity may make patients feel uncontrollable, powerless, and helpless, as well as anxious, fearful, and dismal about the future, which may raise stress levels, worsen depressive symptoms, and lead to suicide ideation (Gangon et al., 1998).

Yıldız et al. (2013) suggests using psychotherapy approaches such cognitive behavioral therapy, acceptance and attachment therapy, mindfulness, and meditation to treat bipolar illness effectively. These strategies may help patients perceive uncertainty more positively, learn to accept and manage with uncertainty, become more flexible and adaptive to uncertainty, decrease anxiety, depression, and stress symptoms, and improve their overall well-being. Şen and Yıldız (2013).

Bipolar Disorder and Obsessions

Obsessions are ideas that occur frequently and involuntarily, causing the individual to be troubled. People with bipolar illness may also exhibit signs of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD). When bipolar illness and OCD coexist, the condition progresses, treatment response reduces, suicide risk rises, and quality of life declines. Bipolar disease and OCD are challenging to treat together since medications lessen OCD symptoms but may produce periods of mania in bipolar disorder. Alternative treatment approaches, such as cognitive behavioral therapy or electroconvulsive therapy, may be used in combination with mood stabilizers and antipsychotic drugs (Öztürk & Uluşahin, 2008).

Bipolar Disorder and Impulsivity

Impulsivity is defined as behaving without thinking, making choices without contemplating the implications, failing to plan, being unable to postpone, and losing control of oneself. People with bipolar disorder may exhibit impulsivity, particularly during mania or hypomania. Impulsivity is linked to more severe symptoms, more frequent episodes, increased drug use, a greater risk of suicide, and worse functioning in bipolar illness. Impulsivity may be

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caused by an imbalance of neurotransmitters in the brain, including dopamine, serotonin, and noradrenaline. Öztürk and Uluşahin (2008) suggest that medicine, psychotherapy, and behavior modification strategies may help lower impulsivity.

Bipolar Disorder and Sleep

Sleep is vital for both physical and mental wellbeing. Sleep relaxes the body, regulates brain processes, boosts the immune system, improves mood, and enhances learning and memory abilities. Sleep enhances one's quality of life and functioning.

Bipolar disorder refers to a bipolar mood condition. In this illness, the individual experiences two distinct mood states: mania and sadness. During mania, the individual becomes too enthusiastic, active, self-confident, chatty, participates in dangerous conduct, and has a reduced need for sleep. During depression, the individual feels unhappy, powerless, useless, guilty, hopeless, apathetic, exhausted, and has difficulty sleeping. Between these two mood phases, there may be a time known as the normal mood period. During this time, the individual does not exhibit signs of mania or depression and may live a regular life.

People with bipolar illness may have more sleep difficulties than the general population. Sleep disorders are difficulties that a person has with sleep-related components such as sleep quality, sleep length, sleep patterns, sleep habits, and troubles while sleeping. Sleep difficulties may be both the cause and the result of bipolar disorder and associated conditions.

People with bipolar illness may develop sleep difficulties (Gangon et al., 1998). During the manic stage, sleep issues may worsen, the individual may need less sleep, sleep less, sleep patterns may be interrupted, sleep habits may alter, and difficulties may arise when sleeping. For example, the individual may remain awake at night instead of sleeping, be busy during the day instead of resting, alter sleep hours often, ignore pre- or post-sleep routines, and suffer from restlessness, nightmares, sleep talking, and sleepwalking while sleeping. During the depressed phase, sleep issues may lessen, the individual may need more sleep, sleep more, sleep patterns may be interrupted, sleep habits may alter, and sleep difficulties may arise. For example, the individual may be unable to sleep at night, fall asleep during the day, alter sleeping hours regularly, disregard pre- or post-sleep routines, and suffer restlessness, nightmares, sleep

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talking, and sleepwalking while sleeping. During the normal mood phase, sleep disorders may recover to normal levels; the individual requires regular sleep, sleeps normally, forms a normal sleep pattern, maintains normal sleep habits, and has no sleep issues.

Sleep disturbances may have an impact on the intensity of symptoms as well as the progression of bipolar illness. Sleep difficulties may influence the frequency, length, intensity, and content of a person's manic and depressive episodes. People with sleep difficulties, for example, may experience mania or depression more often, for longer periods of time, with more severity and complexity. Sleep disturbances may also influence a patient's reaction to therapy. People with sleep difficulties, for example, may struggle to adhere to therapy, have more side effects, need more drug modifications, and be more treatment resistant.

People diagnosed with bipolar illness are advised to take regular medication, follow sleep hygiene principles, monitor their sleeping habits, and seek appropriate therapy if they have sleep issues. Taking medicine on a daily basis helps to minimize sleep disturbances and calm one's mood. Following sleep hygiene standards helps to improve a person's sleep quality and length. Sleep hygiene principles are the actions that a person should and should not engage in before to and after sleep. For example, staying away from stimulating substances such as caffeine, alcohol, and cigarettes before bed, not eating, not exercising, removing disturbing elements such as light, sound, and temperature, engaging in relaxing activities, determining sleep time, and implementing sleep rituals can all be considered complying with sleep hygiene rules. Tracking sleep habits allows a person to analyze, assess, and improve their sleeping patterns. Tracking sleep patterns enables a person to record, evaluate, and improve sleep hours, length, quality, issues encountered while sleeping, emotions felt after sleeping, and other sleep-related elements. If a sleep disorder exists, obtaining adequate treatment assists the individual in determining the source, nature, severity, and implications of the sleep problem, as well as selecting and implementing suitable treatment choices such as medication, psychotherapy, devices, and surgery for sleep disorders.

The link between bipolar illness and sleep is an essential aspect of both the condition and therapy. Sleep difficulties influence how a person copes with bipolar illness, receives treatment, and lives (Gangon et al., 1998).

Bipolar Disorder and Sexuality

Sexuality refers to a person's physical, emotional, and social sexual orientation, as well as their sexual identity, behavior, fantasies, wants, pleasures, and functions. According to Öztürk and Uluşahin (2008), sexuality has a significant impact on individuals' lives, health, happiness, and relationships.

Bipolar disorder refers to a bipolar mood condition. In this illness, the individual experiences two distinct mood states: mania and sadness. During mania, the individual becomes too enthusiastic, active, self-confident, chatty, participates in dangerous conduct, and has a reduced need for sleep. During depression, the individual feels unhappy, powerless, useless, guilty, hopeless, apathetic, exhausted, and has difficulty sleeping. Between these two mood phases, there may be a time known as the normal mood period. During this time, the individual does not exhibit signs of mania or depression and may live a regular life.

People with bipolar illness may exhibit different levels of sexual activity and dysfunction than the general population. Sexual activity includes sexual intercourse, sexual desire, masturbation, and sexual fantasies. Sexual dysfunctions are difficulties that arise during or during sexual activity. Sexual dysfunctions include issues such as sexual hesitation, a lack of sexual excitement, difficulty to orgasm, premature ejaculation, erection difficulties, vaginismus, and dyspareunia.

People suffering from bipolar illness may experience changes in sexual activity and dysfunction. During the manic stage, sexual activity may increase; the individual may have greater sexual desire, seek more sexual partners, take more sexual risks, and have more sexual issues. For example, a person may have more frequent sexual intercourse, experience sexual arousal more easily, masturbate more frequently, have more diverse and extreme sexual fantasies, change sexual partners more frequently, engage in unprotected sexual intercourse, be infected with sexually transmitted diseases, or be subjected to sexual harassment or violence. During depression, sexual activity may diminish, resulting in less sexual desire, fewer sexual partners, less sexual pleasure, and more sexual issues. For example, the person may be less likely to engage in sexual intercourse, have more difficulty with sexual arousal, masturbate less, have fewer sexual fantasies and be pessimistic, find fewer sexual partners, avoid sexual intercourse, be protected against sexually

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transmitted diseases, or be protected against sexual harassment or violence. It is possible that you may have sexual dysfunction. During a normal mood phase, sexual activity and dysfunctions recover to normal levels, allowing for normal sexual desire, partner-finding, pleasure, and issues (Öztürk & Uluşahin, 2008).

Sexual activity and dysfunctions have an impact on treatment adherence, relationship quality, quality of life, and suicide risk in bipolar illness. Sexual activity and sexual dysfunctions may make it harder for the individual to adhere to drug treatment; sexual issues may arise as a result of drug side effects; the dose or kind of medications may impact sexual activity; and the time or frequency with which drugs are taken may hinder sexual activity. Sexual activity and sexual dysfunctions can have a negative impact on a person's relationship, causing problems such as sexual incompatibility, sexual dissatisfaction, sexual insecurity, sexual conflict, sexual infidelity, and sexual separation, as well as causing damage to elements such as commitment, trust, respect, love, and communication. Sexual activity and sexual dysfunctions can lower a person's quality of life by affecting factors such as sexual self-esteem, sexual identity, sexual role, and sexual satisfaction, as well as feelings such as sexual stress, sexual anxiety, sexual depression, and sexual guilt. Sexual function, sexual health, and sexual goals such as happiness may become unattainable. Sexual activity and sexual dysfunction might raise a person's risk of suicide. Sexual issues may lead to feelings like losing hope in life, not finding purpose in life, viewing life as useless, and wanting to end it, as well as activities like self-harm, suicide attempts, and suicide.

- *To improve sexual activity and dysfunction, individuals with bipolar illness should adhere to medication, treatment, education, and awareness of sexual health. Being compliant with medication treatment enables the individual to take his medications on a regular and correct basis, to share the side effects of the medications with his doctor, to change the dosage or type of medications with his doctor's approval, and to adjust the time or frequency of taking medications in response to sexual activity. Receiving sexual education ensures that a person has correct and up-to-date knowledge about sexuality, dispels sexual myths and false ideas, teaches sexual rights and responsibilities, and raises awareness about sexual health and cleanliness. Being sexually aware allows a person to be protected from sexually transmitted diseases, to avoid sexual abuse and violence, to respect his sexual preference and identity, to choose*

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his sexual partner, to have sexual intercourse if he consents, to be protected during sexual intercourse, and to take the necessary precautions following sexual intercourse.

The link between bipolar illness and sexuality is a critical aspect of both the condition and therapy. Sexual activity and sexual dysfunctions influence how a person deals with bipolar illness, how they are treated, and how they live. Medication, psychotherapy, and lifestyle modifications may all help improve sexual activity and dysfunction. As a result, a person with bipolar illness may live a more fulfilling life.

Bipolar Disorder and Temperament

Temperament is an individual's intrinsic, permanent, and unchanging emotional makeup. Temperament governs how a person feels, expresses, and manages his or her emotions. Temperament influences a person's personality, character, conduct, and mood. Temperament also influences a person's interaction with his surroundings, stress management strategies, adaptability, and overall quality of life.

Temperament may be assessed across a variety of parameters. Some of the dimensions are:

- *Way of expressing emotions: It is the tendency to show one's emotions openly or secretly. People with an open temperament easily reveal their emotions, while people with a secret temperament keep their emotions to themselves.*
- *Speed of reaction to stimuli: It is the person's tendency to react quickly or slowly to stimuli. People with a fast temperament react to stimuli immediately and strongly, while people with a slow temperament react to stimuli with a delay and weakly.*
- *Time to get used to stimuli: It is the person's tendency to get used to or satiate the stimuli. People with short temperaments get used to stimuli quickly and get bored, while people with long temperaments get used to stimuli slowly and become interested in them.*
- *Emotional intensity: How intensely a person tends to experience emotions. People with intense temperaments experience their emotions deeply and strongly, while people with weak temperaments experience their emotions superficially and lightly.*

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- *Emotional lability: How frequently and suddenly a person's emotions tend to change. People with a changeable temperament change their emotions easily and frequently, while people with a fixed temperament change their emotions rarely and slowly.*
- *Emotional continuity: How long a person's emotions tend to persist. People with permanent temperament retain their emotions for a long time, while people with temporary temperament retain their emotions for a short time.*
- *Emotional compatibility: The extent to which a person's emotions tend to be appropriate to their environment. People with harmonious temperament adjust their emotions according to their environment, while people with maladaptive temperament do not change their emotions according to their environment.*

People with bipolar disorder may vary from the general population in terms of temperament traits. Bipolar disorder refers to a bipolar mood condition. In this illness, the individual experiences two distinct mood states: mania and sadness. During mania, the individual becomes too enthusiastic, active, self-confident, chatty, participates in dangerous conduct, and has a reduced need for sleep. During depression, a person feels unhappy, powerless, useless, guilty, hopeless, apathetic, exhausted, and has difficulty sleeping. Between these two mood phases, there may be a time known as the normal mood period. During this time, the individual does not exhibit signs of mania or depression and may live a regular life.

People with bipolar disorder may vary in the following temperamental characteristics:

- *Way of expressing emotions: People with bipolar disorder may experience changes in the way they express their emotions. During mania, they may show their emotions openly and excessively. During depression, they may show their emotions in a hidden and repressed way. During normal mood periods, they may show their emotions in a moderate and appropriate manner.*
- *Speed of responding to stimuli: People with bipolar disorder may experience changes in the speed of responding to stimuli. During mania, they may respond quickly and strongly to stimuli. During depression, they may react slowly and poorly to stimuli .*

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During the normal mood period, they can respond to stimuli in a normal and balanced manner.

- *Time to get used to stimuli: People with bipolar disorder may experience changes in the time it takes to get used to stimuli. During the mania period, they may quickly get used to stimuli and become bored. During depression, they may get used to stimuli for a long time and may not be interested in them. During the normal mood period, they can get used to and attend to stimuli in an average time.*
- *Emotional intensity: People with bipolar disorder may experience changes in emotional intensity. During the mania period, they may experience their emotions intensely and violently. During depression, they may experience their emotions in a weak and pale way. During the normal mood period, they can experience their emotions in a moderate and appropriate manner.*
- *Emotional lability: People with bipolar disorder may experience changes in emotional lability. During mania, emotions may change frequently and suddenly. During depression, emotions may remain constant and monotonous. During his normal mood period, his emotions may change infrequently and slowly.*
- *Emotional continuity: People with bipolar disorder may experience changes in emotional continuity. During mania, they may hold their emotions for short periods of time and forget about them. During depression, they may retain their emotions for a long time and not be able to get rid of them. During the normal mood period, they can hold and change their emotions for a normal period of time.*
- *Emotional adaptability: People with bipolar disorder may experience changes in emotional adaptability. During the mania period, they may show their emotions in an inappropriate way to their environment. During depression, they may show their emotions in a way that does not adapt to their environment. During normal mood periods, they can show their emotions in a way appropriate to their environment.*

Temperament may influence both the intensity of symptoms and the progression of the illness in bipolar disorder. Temperament qualities influence the frequency, length, intensity, and content of a person's manic and depression episodes. People with clear, swift, short, intense, variable, persistent, and maladaptive temperaments, for example, may suffer from more frequent, longer, more severe, and complicated manic episodes. People with latent, sluggish,

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lengthy, weak, permanent, transitory, and harmonious temperaments may have more frequent, longer, severe, and simpler depression episodes. Temperament qualities may also influence a person's responsiveness to therapy. People with clear, rapid, short, intense, changeable, persistent, and maladaptive temperaments, for example, may struggle to adjust to therapy, have more side effects, need more drug modifications, and show more treatment resistance. People with latent, sluggish, protracted, weak, fixed, transient, and obedient temperaments may adapt to therapy more quickly, have fewer side effects, need fewer prescription modifications, and have less treatment resistance.

Medication, psychotherapy, and lifestyle modifications may all help to improve someone's temperament. Drug therapy may be tailored to the individual's temperament features. People with clear, rapid, brief, intense, changeable, persistent, and maladaptive temperaments may need more mood stabilizing, antipsychotic, and anxiolytic drugs. People with secretive, sluggish, lengthy, weak, fixed, transient, and harmonious temperaments may need more antidepressant, stimulant, and normothymic medications. Psychotherapy may assist a person in recognizing, understanding, accepting, and managing temperament traits. People with open, rapid, short, intense, variable, consistent, and incompatible temperaments, for example, may learn to regulate their emotions, relax, be cautious, prepare ahead of time, adapt, and think optimistically. People with secretive, sluggish, lengthy, weak, permanent, transitory, and harmonious temperaments may learn to express themselves, take action, be engaged, encouraged, open to change, and feel good. Lifestyle adjustments may assist a person in living a life that is more suitable for their temperament. People with clear, rapid, short, intense, variable, consistent, and incompatible temperaments, for example, may balance their temperaments by engaging in activities such as regular sleep, proper eating, regular exercise, stress reduction, abstaining from alcohol and drugs, and regulating social connections. People with secretive, sluggish, lengthy, weak, fixed, transient, and harmonious temperaments may improve their temperament by getting enough sleep, eating well, exercising regularly, managing stress, abstaining from alcohol and other drugs, and improving social ties.

The link between bipolar illness and temperament is critical to understanding both the condition and its treatment. Temperament qualities influence how a person deals with bipolar illness, receives treatment, and lives. Medication, psychotherapy, and lifestyle modifications may all help to modify temperament traits. As a result, a person with bipolar illness may live a more fulfilling life.

Neurocognitive Functions in Bipolar Disorder

Neurocognitive functions in bipolar disorder are cognitive abilities that a person has based on brain function. Cognitive talents refer to a person's capacity to perceive, process, store, recall, and utilize information. Cognitive abilities are essential in many aspects of everyday living. For example, attention encompasses the capacity to concentrate, selective perception, split perception, and sustained perception. Memory refers to a person's capacity to retain knowledge for short or extended periods of time and remember it when needed. Learning is an individual's capacity to absorb, comprehend, and integrate new knowledge. Planning is the capacity to identify, prioritize, and arrange actions toward achieving one's objectives. Decision making refers to a person's capacity to analyze options, make decisions, and forecast results. Problem solving is the capacity to recognize problems, devise solutions, apply them, and assess their effectiveness. Language refers to a person's capacity to communicate, comprehend, and express themselves vocally or in writing. Motor abilities are defined as the capacity to control one's muscles, coordinate movements, and move.

People suffering from bipolar illness may have impaired neurocognitive skills. Bipolar disorder refers to a bipolar mood condition. In this illness, the individual experiences two distinct mood states: mania and sadness. During mania, the individual becomes too enthusiastic, active, self-confident, chatty, participates in dangerous conduct, and has a reduced need for sleep. During depression, the individual feels unhappy, powerless, useless, guilty, hopeless, apathetic, exhausted, and has difficulty sleeping. Between these two mood phases, there may be a time known as the normal mood period. During this time, the individual does not exhibit signs of mania or depression and may live a regular life.

Neurocognitive processes may influence both the intensity of symptoms and the course of the illness in bipolar disorder. During the manic stage, neurocognitive skills may improve, but this improvement is temporary and may often lead to wrong or hazardous judgments. For example, a person may excessively distract his attention, misuse his memory, exaggerate the information he has learned, act unplanned and rashly, make risky and bad decisions, lose problem-solving skills, use his language excessively and incompatibly, and use his motor skills in an uncontrolled and dangerous manner. During depression, neurocognitive functions

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may diminish, reducing a person's functioning and quality of life. For example, the person may be unable to concentrate, his memory may deteriorate, he may have learning difficulties, he may be unable to plan, he may be indecisive and pessimistic, he may lose problem-solving abilities, he may use his language in a limited and negative manner, and he may use his motor skills slowly and with difficulty. Although neurocognitive skills may improve throughout the normal mood period, this recovery may not be complete, preventing the individual from returning to his prior level. A person can, for example, focus his attention better, remember his memory better, increase his learning capacity, make plans, make decisions, solve problems, use his language to communicate better, and use his motor skills to move better, but these skills cannot be improved when compared to healthy people. may be at a lower level.

To enhance neurocognitive functioning, patients with bipolar illness must adhere to both medication and treatment. Medication helps to alleviate symptoms of mania and depression while also stabilizing mood. Psychotherapy, on the other hand, educates the patient about his condition, teaches coping techniques, alters negative ideas and beliefs, improves social skills, and improves quality of life. Furthermore, persons with bipolar disease who get cognitive rehabilitation, do brain exercises, and live a healthy lifestyle help to improve neurocognitive skills. Cognitive rehabilitation assesses a person's neurocognitive capabilities, detects inadequacies, builds on strengths, improves cognitive skills, teaches cognitive methods, and enhances functioning. Brain workouts are activities that engage, challenge, and develop a person's cognitive abilities. Brain workouts include activities such as solving puzzles, playing sudoku, learning a foreign language, playing a musical instrument, singing, drawing, reading, and writing. Maintaining a healthy lifestyle is the activity that a person should engage in to safeguard his bodily and mental health. Sleeping regularly, eating properly, exercising frequently, avoiding stress, abstaining from alcohol and other drugs, and improving social interactions are all examples of healthy lifestyle activities.

Neurocognitive functions in bipolar illness play a significant role in both the disease and therapy. Neurocognitive functions influence a person's cognitive abilities, everyday living, functioning, quality of life, treatment adherence, and suicide risk. To increase neurocognitive functioning, a person must seek expert guidance and adopt lifestyle modifications. As a result, a person may manage with bipolar illness more effectively and enhance their quality of life.

Comorbidity in Bipolar Disorder

The comorbidity of bipolar illness is the individual's degree of interest, activity, and liveliness toward the outside world. A comorbidity may disrupt a person's life in a variety of ways. For example, a person with high comorbidity may be more effective in social interactions, more passionate about their interests, more involved in leisure activities, more efficient in their job performance, and have a greater quality of life. A low score may cause a person to retreat from social interactions, be less engaged in hobbies, be indifferent to leisure activities, do poorly at work, and be dissatisfied with their quality of life.

People with bipolar illness may have fluctuating levels of comorbidity. Bipolar disorder refers to a bipolar mood condition. In this illness, the individual experiences two distinct mood states: mania and sadness. During mania, the individual becomes too enthusiastic, active, self-confident, chatty, participates in dangerous conduct, and has a reduced need for sleep. During depression, the individual feels unhappy, powerless, useless, guilty, hopeless, apathetic, exhausted, and has difficulty sleeping. Between these two mood phases, there may be a time known as the normal mood period. During this time, the individual does not exhibit signs of mania or depression and may live a regular life.

Comorbidity may have an impact on both the intensity of symptoms and the progression of the illness in bipolar disorder. As comorbidity grows throughout the manic stage, the individual may encounter additional issues. For example, the individual may overspend, ruin relationships, lose their job, encounter legal issues, or endanger themselves or others. As the comorbidity lowers throughout the depressive stage, the individual may suffer more. For example, a person may become socially alienated, feel worthless, contemplate suicide, or be unable to enjoy life. The severity of comorbidity may also influence the frequency of attacks. People with a high comorbidity may have more frequent mania bouts. People with minimal comorbidity may have more bouts of depression. The amount of comorbidity may also influence the response to therapy. People with high comorbidities may believe they do not need therapy or that drugs slow them down, prompting them to discontinue treatment. People with low comorbidity may have lost hope in therapy and may not cooperate with it.

Consequently, those diagnosed with bipolar illness must adhere to both medication and treatment. Medication helps to alleviate symptoms of mania and depression while also

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stabilizing mood. Psychotherapy, on the other hand, educates the patient about his condition, teaches coping techniques, alters negative ideas and beliefs, improves social skills, and improves quality of life. Furthermore, persons with bipolar illness should develop their social support networks, manage stress, pay attention to their sleep patterns, eat well, exercise frequently, and avoid alcohol and other drugs, all of which will help to balance the amount of comorbidity.

Comorbidity in bipolar illness is a significant aspect of both the condition and its treatment. The severity of comorbidity influences a person's mood, behavior, issues, and successes. Extra To achieve balance, the individual must seek professional aid as well as make lifestyle modifications. As a result, a person with bipolar illness may live a more fulfilling life.

Anxiety Sensitivity in Bipolar Disorder

Anxious sensitivity in bipolar illness refers to the dread of anxious symptoms or their repercussions. Anxiety sensitivity is a key factor in the development and maintenance of anxiety disorders. People with high anxiety sensitivity feel that anxiety symptoms are physiologically, mentally, or socially detrimental, that they are uncontrolled, and that they will progress to other mental health issues. People with high anxiety sensitivity avoid circumstances that cause anxiety symptoms, attempt to repress anxiety symptoms, rely on others for relief, and utilize drugs to alleviate anxiety symptoms. These actions enhance anxiety sensitivity, causing anxiety disorders to develop and persist.

Anxiety sensitivity may occur in people with bipolar illness since anxiety symptoms are a feature of the disease. Bipolar disorder is a mental condition characterized by significant mood fluctuations that alternate between manic and depressed episodes. During a manic episode, the individual may be very joyful, active, self-confident, ambitious, chatty, enthusiastic, and engage in dangerous conduct. During a depressive episode, the individual may feel very unhappy, weary, hopeless, useless, guilty, apathetic, and suicidal thoughts. These mood shifts may also result in anxiety symptoms. Anxiety symptoms include heart palpitations, shortness of breath, perspiration, tremors, dizziness, nausea, muscular tension, sleeplessness, problems focusing, excessive worrying, fear, panic, avoidance, obsession, and compulsion. People with bipolar disorder may be concerned that their anxiety symptoms may hurt themselves or others, provoke

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bipolar disorder episodes, or interfere with bipolar disorder therapy. This worry heightens anxiety sensitivity, exacerbates bipolar disorder symptoms, makes episodes more frequent, and further impairs bipolar disease functioning.

Anxiety sensitivity is linked to more severe symptoms, more frequent episodes, worse functioning, greater drug use, and a higher risk of suicide in bipolar illness. People with bipolar illness who have a high anxiety sensitivity suffer more severe symptoms because anxiety sensitivity promotes mood swings and fluctuations. People with bipolar illness who have high anxiety sensitivity have more bipolar disorder episodes because anxiety sensitivity increases stress, anxiety, despair, rage, and guilt. People with bipolar illness who have high anxiety sensitivity have worse bipolar disorder functioning because anxiety sensitivity has a detrimental impact on social interactions, job performance, academic accomplishment, and everyday activities. People with bipolar illness who have high anxiety sensitivity are more likely to use substances like alcohol, cigarettes, and narcotics to relieve their anxiety symptoms. People with bipolar disease who have high anxiety sensitivity are more likely to commit suicide because anxiety sensitivity lowers self-confidence, self-esteem, self-love, and pleasure of life.

To lower anxiety sensitivity, patients with bipolar disorder should follow their medication regimen, undertake cognitive behavioral therapy, acquire anxiety management strategies, and build stress coping abilities. Medication is an effective way to lessen bipolar illness and anxiety symptoms while also stabilizing mood and anxiety sensitivity. Mood stabilizers, antidepressants, antipsychotics, and anxiolytics are all drugs that may be used for therapy. Cognitive behavioral therapy is a kind of psychotherapy that assists individuals with bipolar illness in changing thinking and behavior patterns that produce anxiety sensitivity, reducing anxiety sensitivity, and improving anxiety management abilities. Cognitive behavioral therapy addresses ideas such as cognitive distortions, automatic thinking, negative attitudes, and illogical thoughts that induce anxiety sensitivity. Anxiety management approaches educate people with bipolar illness how to detect anxiety symptoms, regulate them, lessen anxiety symptoms, reduce anxiety sensitivity, and reinforce anxiety management abilities. Techniques for anxiety treatment include breathing exercises, relaxation exercises, diversion activities, positive recommendations, and problem-solving exercises.

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Body Perception in Bipolar Disorder

Body image disturbance may be both a result and a cause of bipolar illness. Body perception refers to how a person perceives, assesses, and experiences his or her own body. Body image influences a person's self-esteem, self-love, and overall quality of life. People with a positive body perspective see their own bodies as realistic, healthy, and attractive; they accept, respect, and adore their own bodies. People with a negative body view, on the other hand, see their own bodies as unreal, ill, and unattractive, reject them, disregard them, and gaze at them with contempt.

People with bipolar illness may have body image issues since the disease may produce negative ideas and emotions regarding body image. Bipolar disorder is a mental condition characterized by significant mood fluctuations that alternate between manic and depressed episodes. During a manic episode, the individual may be very joyful, active, self-confident, ambitious, chatty, enthusiastic, and engage in dangerous conduct. During a depressive episode, the individual may feel very unhappy, weary, hopeless, useless, guilty, apathetic, and suicidal thoughts. These emotional shifts may also have an impact on how a person perceives their physique. During the manic stage, the individual may exaggerately appreciate his or her own physique, be too interested in it, continually want to modify it, and try to exhibit it to others. During a depressed episode, the individual may excessively criticize his or her own body, exhibit indifference to his or her own body, give up on improving his or her own body, and attempt to conceal his or her body from others. This body image issue may exacerbate a person's bipolar disorder symptoms, increase the frequency of bipolar disorder episodes, and limit bipolar illness functioning even further.

Body image issues are linked to more severe symptoms, more frequent episodes, worse functioning, more eating disorders, more sexual dysfunction, and a greater risk of suicide in bipolar illness. People with bipolar illness who also have body dysmorphic disorder suffer from bipolar disorder symptoms more severely because their body image disruption causes their mood to fluctuate and shift more. People with bipolar illness who also have body image problem have more bipolar disorder episodes because body image disorder causes increased stress, anxiety, melancholy, rage, and guilt. People with bipolar illness who suffer from body image disturbance have poorer bipolar disorder functioning because body image disorder has a detrimental impact on social interactions, employment performance, academic

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accomplishment, and everyday activities. People with bipolar disease who suffer from body image problems are more likely to develop eating disorders, since body image disorders impair eating behaviors, weight management, and eating patterns. People with bipolar illness who suffer from body image disorder are more likely to develop sexual dysfunction because body image disorder impairs sexual desire, sexual performance, sexual pleasure, and sexual identity. People with bipolar disease are more likely to commit suicide because body perception disorder affects self-confidence, self-esteem, self-love, and enjoyment of life.

People with bipolar illness are advised to follow pharmaceutical treatment, get psychotherapy, use body positivity strategies, and prioritize physical wellness in order to enhance their body image. Medication effectively reduces bipolar illness symptoms, stabilizes mood, and improves bodily perception. Mood stabilizers, antidepressants, antipsychotics, and anxiolytics are all drugs that may be used for therapy. Psychotherapy is a therapeutic strategy that teaches people with bipolar illness about the origins, consequences, and coping strategies for body perception disorder, as well as how to modify negative thoughts and emotions about body perception and positively enhance it. Psychotherapy may take several forms, including individual treatment, group therapy, and family therapy. Body positivity approaches help people with bipolar illness embrace, respect, and love their own bodies, reinforce good ideas and emotions about their bodies, and positively modify their perceptions of their bodies. Body positivity strategies include body positive expressions, body positivity exercises, body positivity meditation, and a body positivity journal. Paying attention to physical health is a practice that allows a person with bipolar illness to maintain their own body healthy, take excellent care of their own body, safeguard their own body, improve positive thoughts and emotions regarding body perception, and have a positive impact on body perception. Physical health may be maintained via regular exercise, a nutritious diet, attention to sleep patterns, abstaining from alcohol and smoking, and focusing on personal care.

Emotion Regulation Difficulties in Bipolar Disorder

One of the most significant characteristics of bipolar illness is difficulty with emotion management. Emotion regulation is the capacity to detect, express, control, and modify one's emotions. Emotion regulation influences a person's psychological health, functioning,

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relationships, and overall quality of life. People with strong emotion management abilities can express themselves effectively, keep their emotions under control, transform their feelings positively, communicate their emotions with others, and resolve their emotions appropriately. People with poor emotion regulation abilities may express their feelings improperly, be unable to manage their emotions, modify their emotions badly, be unable to communicate their emotions with others, or resolve their emotions inappropriately.

People with bipolar illness may struggle to regulate their emotions since the disease causes great lability and intensity. Bipolar disorder is a mental condition characterized by significant mood fluctuations that alternate between manic and depressed episodes. During a manic episode, the individual may be very joyful, active, self-confident, ambitious, chatty, enthusiastic, and engage in dangerous conduct. During a depressive episode, the individual may feel very unhappy, weary, hopeless, useless, guilty, apathetic, and suicidal thoughts. These mood swings may make it challenging for a person to detect, express, regulate, and modify their feelings. Emotion regulation issues in bipolar disorder indicate that the individual is unable to handle their emotional emotions effectively. This may have a detrimental impact on the clinical course, functioning, and relationships of bipolar disorder.

Emotion regulation issues in bipolar disease are linked to a variety of causes, including childhood trauma, genetic susceptibility, chemical imbalances in the brain, and stressful life experiences. Childhood traumas may contribute to the development of bipolar illness and emotional control issues. People who were physically, emotionally, or sexually abused as children, neglected, exposed to violence, suffered loss, or had family troubles may be more likely to develop bipolar illness and emotional regulation issues. A family history of bipolar illness and difficulty with emotion control may be influenced by genetic susceptibility. First-degree relatives of persons with bipolar illness are more likely to have the disease or struggle with emotional management. Bipolar illness and difficulty regulating emotions may be caused by chemical imbalances in the brain. Imbalanced neurotransmitters in the brain, such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine, may cause severe mood swings and issues with emotional control. Stressful life situations might exacerbate bipolar illness and emotional control issues. Divorce, job loss, death, disease, and trauma may all result in bipolar disorder recurrence and increased emotional control issues.

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Medication, psychotherapy, emotion regulation skills training, and cognitive behavioral therapy are all options for treating emotional control problems in bipolar disorder. Medication is an effective way to lessen bipolar illness symptoms, regulate mood, and avoid issues with emotional control. Mood stabilizers, antidepressants, antipsychotics, and anxiolytics are all drugs that may be used for therapy. Psychotherapy is a therapeutic strategy that discusses the reasons, consequences, and coping strategies for people with bipolar illness, as well as helping them strengthen their emotion regulation abilities and lessen their emotion regulation challenges. Psychotherapy may take several forms, including individual treatment, group therapy, and family therapy. Emotion regulation skills training is a training program that teaches people with bipolar illness how to detect, express, regulate, and modify their feelings, minimizes emotion regulation challenges, and strengthens emotion regulation abilities. Emotion regulation skills training includes themes such as emotion awareness, emotion identification, emotion expression, emotion management, emotion modification, and emotion resolution. Cognitive behavioral therapy is a kind of psychotherapy that assists individuals with bipolar illness in changing thinking and behavior patterns that create emotion regulation issues, reducing emotion regulation challenges, and improving emotion regulation abilities. Cognitive distortions, automatic thoughts, negative ideas, and illogical thoughts are all included in cognitive behavioral therapy as causes of emotion control issues.

Dyadic adjustment in bipolar disorder

It refers to the quality and harmony of a bipolar person's relationship with their spouse or partner. Bipolar disorder is a mental condition characterized by significant mood fluctuations that alternate between manic and depressed episodes. People with bipolar illness may face issues for themselves as well as others with whom they are in relationships as a result of emotional volatility. Factors influencing dyadic adjustment in bipolar disorder include the severity, frequency, and duration of symptoms, the partner's knowledge and attitude toward bipolar disorder, the couple's communication and problem-solving skills, and the couple's social support resources.

Dyadic adjustment is an essential aspect of bipolar disorder therapy. People with bipolar illness who have a high dyadic adjustment adhere to treatment better, have fewer relapses, a

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higher quality of life, and fewer suicide thoughts and attempts. People with bipolar illness who have poor dyadic adjustment have worse treatment compliance, more frequent relapses, a lower quality of life, and are more likely to have suicide thoughts or attempts. As a result, improving dyadic adjustment in bipolar illness is critical for the health and happiness of both the individual and their spouse.

pair therapy, partner education, and family therapy may all help improve pair harmony in bipolar illness. Couples therapy is a form of psychotherapy that seeks to promote communication, understanding, love, respect, and trust between a bipolar patient and their spouse. Couples therapy teaches couples how to lessen the consequences of bipolar disorder, solve bipolar disorder-related difficulties, avoid bipolar disorder recurrence, and support bipolar disorder treatment. Couple therapy assists a bipolar disease patient's partner in better understanding bipolar disorder, approaching the patient more effectively, and providing greater support. Couple therapy helps people with bipolar disease better understand their partner's emotions and needs, communicate with them, and treat them better.

Spouse education is an educational program that gives information on bipolar illness to a person's spouse, encourages engagement in bipolar disorder treatment, and teaches methods to prevent bipolar disorder from recurring. Spouse education teaches them about the symptoms of bipolar disorder, its causes, treatment techniques, the benefits and side effects of drugs, factors that cause bipolar disorder to return, and what has to be done to prevent it from reoccurring. Spouse education teaches spouses how to better assist the person with bipolar disorder, work with the person with bipolar illness, and adjust to the person's therapy.

Family therapy is a sort of psychotherapy that improves connections between people with bipolar disease and their families, helps family members learn about bipolar disorder, and helps family members assist the person with bipolar disorder more effectively. In family therapy, family members learn ways to decrease the consequences of bipolar disorder, address bipolar disorder-related difficulties, and participate to bipolar disorder treatment. Family therapy helps family members to better understand, love, respect, and trust the person with bipolar illness, while also allowing the person with bipolar disease to better understand, love, respect, and trust their family members.

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Dyadic adjustment in bipolar illness is a significant aspect influencing the quality of life and happiness of both the individual with the disease and their spouse. marriage therapy, spouse education, and family therapy may all help improve marriage harmony in bipolar illness. These strategies improve the connection between the person with bipolar disorder and their spouse, make bipolar disorder treatment easier, reduce bipolar disease recurrence, and improve the person's and their partner's health and well-being.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.1. Related Research

- **Gültekin et al. (2013)** evaluated research on bipolar disorder in Turkey. They said that this research had no certified epidemiological field investigations, that the majority of the studies were based on hospital admissions and clinical studies, and that the generalizability of the results to our society was far from legitimate and trustworthy. However, they suggested that a profile established by evaluating the outcomes of research done in various locations of our nation would help to identify the disease's distinctive features and risk factors. They also highlighted the paucity of knowledge on bipolar illness, which might serve as the foundation for the establishment and growth of community mental health services.
- **Aydoğdu and Dirik (2020)** reviewed data on the efficacy of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (FTBT) in bipolar illness. In these studies, it was discovered that MBBT could reduce the symptoms of anxiety, depression, or mania/hypomania in

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people diagnosed with bipolar disorder, and that participants tended to report that this psychotherapy method helped them and increased their level of awareness. Participants' attention, information processing, memory, emotional control, and positive affect were all shown to improve. However, as with cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) research results, these findings are not supported in every study, and the information about whether MBBT provides a decrease in manic and hypomanic symptoms cannot be clarified because the research is generally conducted with people in remission.

- **Özdemir et al. (2018)** examined the correlation between suicide behavior in bipolar disorder patients and their sociodemographic and clinical features, including impulsivity and childhood traumas. The research comprised 100 individuals with bipolar illness and 100 healthy control groups. Suicidal behavior, impulsivity, and childhood traumas of the individuals were assessed. According to the statistics, 40% of bipolar illness individuals had tried suicide at least once in their life. Patients who tried suicide reported greater ratings for impulsivity and childhood trauma compared to those who did not. Patients who attempted suicide were also found to have lower education levels, longer disease durations, and more hospitalizations. These findings indicate that suicidal conduct in bipolar illness is linked to sociodemographic and clinical characteristics, and that impulsivity and childhood traumas increase the risk of suicide.
- **Aksoy's 2019 thesis**, "Evaluation of serum neuroserpin, tPA, IL-6, and BDNF levels in bipolar disorder patients," explored the role of biomarkers in the disease's etiology. According to their results, NSP and tPA levels are considerably lower in the bipolar group than in the control group, whereas IL-6 and BDNF levels are not different.
- **Çetin (2018)** wanted to evaluate whether there is a difference in functioning and reaction levels to preventative therapy based on personality traits in individuals with bipolar illness. The findings revealed a negative significant association between personality characteristics and functioning in patients, as well as a positive significant relationship between personality traits and responsiveness to preventative therapy.
- **Kaya (2019)** studied the correlation between suicide behavior in bipolar illness patients and their sociodemographics, clinical features, impulsivity, and childhood traumas. Their results revealed a substantial link between suicidal behavior and impulsivity, early physical abuse, sexual abuse, and emotional neglect in bipolar illness patients.
- **Ekinci and Tokkaş (2024)** performed a comprehensive assessment of experimental trials assessing the efficacy of story therapy. They merged the study findings with the

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meta-analysis approach and discovered that story therapy is an effective intervention for mental diseases such as depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, and bipolar disorder.

- **Özdemir's 2019** study on bipolar illness patients indicated that social rhythm treatment improved their quality of life, adaptability, functioning, and depression levels.
- **In a study of bipolar disorder patients, Kılıç (2018)** discovered that sleep hygiene training increased sleep quality and cleanliness while reducing despair and anxiety.
- **Yıldız (2017)** found that psychoeducation for bipolar illness patients improved disease knowledge, treatment compliance, quality of life, social support, and stress coping abilities.
- **Güneş (2017)** found that both cognitive behavioral therapy and psychoeducation improved depression, anxiety, functionality, and quality of life in bipolar disorder patients, but cognitive behavioral therapy outperformed psychoeducation.
- **In a study of bipolar illness patients, Koç (2016)** revealed that stress coping methods and social support levels predicted quality of life.
- **Erdem (2019)** examined how comorbid social anxiety disorder affects clinical characteristics, treatment compliance, and quality of life in bipolar disorder patients. According to their results, comorbid social anxiety disorder is common among bipolar disorder patients and has a detrimental impact on the disease's progression.
- **Kurt (2018)** found that oxidative stress contributes to the pathophysiology of bipolar illness. In his investigation, he discovered that serum malondialdehyde, nitric oxide, and superoxide dismutase levels were much greater and catalase levels were significantly lower in bipolar disorder patients than in control subjects.
- **Yılmaz's (2017) thesis**, "Evaluation of serum leptin, adiponectin, and resistin levels in bipolar disorder patients," suggests that these adipokines may contribute to the pathophysiology of bipolar disease. In his investigation, he discovered that blood leptin and resistin levels were considerably greater and adiponectin levels were much lower in bipolar disorder patients than in control subjects.
- **Özdemir's (2016) thesis**, "Evaluation of serum endocannabin-1 levels in bipolar disorder patients," suggests that endocannabin-1 may contribute to the pathogenesis of bipolar

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disease. In his investigation, he discovered that individuals with bipolar illness had much greater blood endocanin-1 levels than the control group.

- **Köse's (2016) thesis**, "Evaluation of hematological parameters such as serum neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio, platelet/lymphocyte ratio, and mean platelet volume in bipolar disorder patients," suggests that these parameters may indicate inflammatory processes in the disease's pathophysiology. His research found that bipolar disorder patients had much greater serum neutrophil/lymphocyte and platelet/lymphocyte ratios than the control group, as well as a significantly lower mean platelet volume.
- Bipolar disorder patients had higher levels of homocysteine, folate, and vitamin B12. **Kara (2015)** proposed that these metabolites might have a role in the etiology of bipolar illness. In his investigation, he discovered that blood homocysteine levels were much higher and folate and vitamin B12 levels were significantly lower in bipolar disorder patients than in control subjects.
- **Özcan's (2015) thesis**, "Evaluation of serum prolactin levels in bipolar disorder patients," suggests that prolactin may contribute to the pathogenesis of bipolar disease. In his investigation, he discovered that blood prolactin levels in bipolar disorder patients were considerably greater than in the control group.
- In his thesis titled "Evaluation of serum calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, and alkaline phosphatase levels in bipolar disorder patients," **Yıldırım (2015)** proposed that these electrolytes and enzymes may contribute to the pathophysiology of bipolar disease. His research found that bipolar disorder patients' blood calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, and alkaline phosphatase levels were not substantially different from the control group.
- **Karaçam's (2014) thesis**, "Evaluation of serum vitamin D levels in bipolar disorder patients," suggests that vitamin D may contribute to the pathogenesis of the condition. In his investigation, he discovered that people with bipolar illness had considerably lower blood vitamin D levels than the control group.
- **In his thesis, Özdemir (2014)** proposed that serum selenium, zinc, and copper levels may contribute to the pathophysiology of bipolar illness. In his investigation, he discovered that blood selenium and zinc levels were much lower and copper levels were significantly greater in bipolar disorder patients than in control subjects.

CHAPTER FIVE

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Bipolar disorder is a psychiatric condition characterized by significant mood fluctuations, including mania and sadness. Jean-Pierre Falret, a French doctor, originally diagnosed bipolar illness as "circular insanity" in 1854. Bipolar disorder is now recognized in worldwide diagnostic systems such as DSM-5 (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of the American Psychiatric Association) and ICD-10 (worldwide Classification of Diseases of the World Health Organization).

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Bipolar disorder is classified into many categories based on diagnostic criteria. Bipolar I disorder affects patients who have at least one episode of mania and one or more bouts of significant depression. Bipolar II disorder affects patients who have at least one episode of hypomania and one or more bouts of significant depression. The manic stage is characterized by an extraordinarily elevated emotional state, increased self-confidence, decreased need for sleep, accelerated speech, volatile ideas, easily diverted attention, and an increase in dangerous conduct. The hypomanic episode is comparable to a manic episode, but with less symptoms. Major depression is characterized by a significant decline in mood, loss of interest and pleasure, sleep and eating disturbances, increased feelings of shame and worthlessness, and suicidal ideation.

The causes of bipolar disorder are not completely understood. However, genetic, biochemical, psychological, and environmental elements are regarded to be useful. Bipolar disorder is more prevalent in those with a family history. Bipolar disorder is characterized by an imbalance of neurotransmitters (serotonin, dopamine, and noradrenaline) in the brain. Personality characteristics, stress coping abilities, emotional regulation mechanisms, cognitive processes, and beliefs are all examples of psychological elements. Environmental influences include life events, seasonal changes, sleep habits, social support, substance abuse, and drug treatment.

Bipolar disorder is a significant condition that impairs one's quality of life, functioning, relationships, and health. Clinical characteristics, course, and result in bipolar illness might vary based on variables such as disease type, severity, duration, frequency, treatment adherence, and comorbidity. Bipolar disorder may have a chronic or recurring history. Bipolar illness increases the likelihood of suicide. Bipolar illness is manageable with adequate therapy and psychological support.

Psychological theories of bipolar illness attempt to explain the disease's psychological causes, as well as its triggering and protecting variables. These ideas also inform the therapy of bipolar illness. Psychological theories include the behavioral activation/inhibition systems model, the interpersonal interactions and social rhythm treatment method, the behavioral sensitization and kindling model, the cognitive behavioral approach, and the psychoanalytic approach.

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The behavioral activation/inhibition systems model studies the link between bipolar illness and personality factors. According to this hypothesis, the behavioral activation system (DAS) is linked to qualities including reward seeking, openness to new experiences, enthusiasm, and enjoyment. The behavioral inhibition system (DIS) is linked to qualities including punishment avoidance, fear, and anxiety. In bipolar disorder, the DAS is assumed to be hyperactive while the DIS is underactive. This scenario causes mania and sadness to arise. This paradigm is utilized for the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of bipolar illness.

The interpersonal interactions and social rhythm treatment method stresses the link of bipolar illness to social and environmental variables. According to this viewpoint, issues in interpersonal connections in bipolar illness, stressful life events, a lack of social support, disturbance of sleep patterns, and changes in daily routines all have an impact on the disease's start, course, and outcomes. This approach to bipolar disease therapy aims to improve interpersonal interactions, regulate social rhythms, and increase stress coping abilities.

The behavioral sensitization and kindling model explain the association between bipolar illness and mood lability. According to this paradigm, bipolar illness patients' moods become hypersensitive to both happy and negative stimuli. This sensitivity makes the mood more unpredictable and the condition more severe. Additionally, persons with bipolar illness employ a mechanism known as kindling to control their mood. Affects are conscious activities that increase or diminish one's mood. During a manic episode, for example, the individual may attempt to elevate his or her mood by engaging in behaviors such as increased socialization, purchasing, and dangerous activities.

The cognitive behavioral approach investigates the link between bipolar illness and cognitive and behavioral characteristics. According to this viewpoint, patients with bipolar illness exhibit cognitive distortions (misinterpretation of reality) in response to their affective states. For example, during a manic episode, a person may believe himself to be very valued, brilliant, powerful, and unique. During depression, a person may feel worthless, inadequate, guilty, and powerless. These cognitive errors weaken mood and promote maladaptive behavior. This method to bipolar disease therapy aims to recognize cognitive distortions, generate alternative and realistic thinking, ensure positive behavioral adjustments, and monitor and manage emotional state.

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The psychoanalytic approach analyzes the link between bipolar illness and psychodynamic causes. According to this theory, persons with bipolar illness are influenced by traumatic events from their upbringing, suppressed emotions, unresolved conflicts, defensive mechanisms, ego development, narcissistic structure, and mother-father relationships. These elements influence a person's emotional state, self-perception, relationship-building style, and sense of purpose. This method to bipolar disease therapy aims to uncover the person's unconscious processes, analyze prior experiences, express emotions, resolve disputes, maintain self-integrity, and improve relationships.

The domains of bipolar disorder explain how the condition impacts several facets of a person's life. Bipolar illness may lead to difficulties in physical, psychological, social, professional, academic, economic, legal, cultural, religious, family, sexual, artistic, and personal growth. Bipolar illness may impair a person's functioning, performance, adjustment, contentment, happiness, health, goals, values, and identity. Bipolar disease may alter a person's interactions with himself, others, the environment, society, nature, and the cosmos in various areas.

Bipolar illness research refers to studies that seek to generate scientific evidence on topics such as diagnosis, treatment, prevention, support, education, awareness, awareness-raising, advocacy, rights protection, social policy, and service provision. Bipolar disorder research investigates the causes of the disease, symptoms, course, consequences, areas of influence, risk and protective factors, psychological mechanisms, treatment methods, treatment effectiveness, treatment compliance, treatment obstacles, treatment needs, treatment expectations, treatment satisfaction, and post-treatment quality of life. , post-treatment functionality, post-treatment recovery, post-treatment relapse, post-treatment support systems, post-treatment social participation, post-treatment stigma, post-treatment rights violations, post-treatment advocacy activities, post-treatment social policy recommendations, and post-treatment service delivery models. Conducts study on certain issues.

Bipolar illness research helps us understand, recognize, accept, treat, prevent, support, enhance, protect, defend, and develop the condition. Bipolar illness research focuses on the individual, family, social, cultural, economic, legal, political, ethical, and scientific aspects of the condition. Bipolar disorder research allows the condition to be treated from a

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multidisciplinary, holistic, human rights-based, participative, empowering, solidaristic, solution-oriented, positive, and hopeful perspective.

Bipolar disorder research takes into account both the illness's positive and bad elements. Bipolar illness may lead to problems, suffering, losses, injuries, damage, victimization, violations, discrimination, stigmatization, loneliness, and despair in a person's life. However, bipolar disease may also lead to chances, advancements, accomplishments, learning, creativity, sensitivity, empathy, perseverance, bravery, originality, independence, and hope in a person's life. Bipolar disorder research aims to lessen the disease's unfavorable parts while increasing its good aspects and improving the person's life.

Bipolar disorder research allows the condition to be addressed from many disciplines, using diverse methodologies, sample groups, and aims, as well as distinct questions, hypotheses, results, interpretations, and recommendations. Bipolar illness research demonstrates that the condition is a multifaceted, multilayered, multicolored, and multivocal phenomena. According to research on bipolar disorder, the disease is more than a diagnosis, a label, a category, a class, a group, a number, or a statistic; it is also a life, an experience, a meaning, a value, an identity, and a distinction. Puts it.

Bipolar illness research stresses the disease's dual nature as an individual and a societal issue. Bipolar disease impairs a person's relationships with himself, his family, friends, coworkers, neighbors, acquaintances, and strangers. Bipolar disease impairs a person's ability to contribute to society, culture, the economy, law, politics, ethics, and science. Bipolar disease influences a person's expectations of society, culture, the economy, law, politics, ethics, and science. Bipolar disease serves as a reminder that each individual is a member of society, culture, economics, law, politics, ethics, and science.

Bipolar illness research suggests that the condition is both problem- and solution-oriented. Bipolar illness displays the issues, challenges, hurdles, deficits, wants, demands, expectations, ambitions, values, and meanings that the individual faces in life. Bipolar disease exposes the answers, facilities, opportunities, supports, resources, tools, techniques, tactics, talents, abilities, strengths, and potentials that the individual wants in life. Bipolar illness demonstrates that there may be both problems and solutions in a person's life.

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Bipolar disorder research reveals that the illness needs both a scientific and a humanitarian approach. Bipolar disorder may be defined, classed, measured, tested, analyzed, interpreted, confirmed, generalized, published, debated, critiqued, and improved using a scientific method. Bipolar illness may be understood, accepted, respected, supported, assisted, healed, protected, defended, developed, shared, loved, and made joyful via a compassionate approach. Bipolar disease demonstrates the need of using both scientific and humanistic approaches.

Bipolar disorder research reveals that the condition is important in both theory and practice. Bipolar disorder is theoretically significant because it describes the causes of the disease, symptoms, course, consequences, areas of influence, risk and protective factors, psychological mechanisms, treatment methods, treatment effectiveness, treatment compliance, treatment obstacles, treatment needs, treatment expectations, treatment satisfaction, post-treatment quality of life, post-treatment functionality, post-treatment recovery process, post-treatment relapse, and post- Bipolar disorder is practical because it is a practice, intervention, action, participation, cooperation, coordination, organization, etc. in areas such as diagnosis, treatment, prevention, support, education, awareness, awareness-raising, advocacy, rights provision, social policy, and service provision. Planning, assessment, monitoring, and reporting are all necessary actions. Bipolar illness demonstrates the necessity of both theory and practice.

According to research, bipolar illness has the capacity to cause both individual and society transformation. Bipolar illness has the ability to produce individual change since it alters the person's life, relationships, objectives, values, meanings, identity, difference, potential, strength, weakness, needs, expectations, demands, rights, responsibilities, choices, decisions, and behaviors. , to change, develop, heal, protect, defend, emotions, thoughts, beliefs, attitudes, evaluations, interpretations, predictions, solutions, strategies, skills, abilities, resources, supports, opportunities, difficulties, obstacles, risks, protectors, healers, developers, It allows people to share, participate, cooperate, coordinate, organize, plan, evaluate, monitor, report, publish, discuss, criticize, learn, teach, create, produce, achieve, be happy, hope, love, and Bipolar illness has the ability to produce social change since it impacts society, including its life, relationships, objectives, values, meanings, identity, variety, potential, strength, weakness, needs, expectations, demands, rights, duties, choices, decisions, and behaviors. , to change, develop, heal, protect, defend, emotions, thoughts, beliefs, attitudes, evaluations, interpretations, predictions, solutions, strategies, skills, abilities, resources, supports,

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opportunities, difficulties, obstacles, risks, protectors, healers, developers, It allows people to share, participate, cooperate, coordinate, organize, plan, evaluate, monitor, report, publish, discuss, criticize, learn, teach, create, produce, achieve, be happy, hope, love, and Bipolar disease indicates that change must be driven by both individual and societal factors.

Bipolar illness research shows that the condition offers scientific and human worth. Bipolar illness has scientific importance because it helps to progress, grow, refresh, diversify, enrich, deepen, expand, disseminate, share, discuss, criticize, learn, teach, create, produce, succeed, be happy, and hope for research. provides. Bipolar disorder has a human value because it enables people to understand, accept, respect, support, help, heal, protect, defend, develop, share, participate, cooperate, coordinate, organize, plan, and evaluate. It also helps with monitoring, reporting, publishing, discussing, criticizing, learning, teaching, creating, producing, achieving, making happy, giving hope, and loving. Bipolar disease demonstrates how science and human values must coexist.

SUGGESTIONS

Bipolar disorder is a psychiatric condition characterized by significant mood swings, including mania, hypomania, and depression 1. Understanding the nature, course, and treatment of bipolar illness depends on its definition and classification. Therefore, our proposals are:

Bipolar disorder should be defined in terms of its variety, complexity, and individual variations. Bipolar illness should be addressed as a spectrum condition, rather than a singular disease.

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When characterizing bipolar disorder, it is important to underline that the condition affects cognitive, behavioral, physiological, and psychosocial domains in addition to mood alterations.

Bipolar disorder should be defined using current scientific evidence regarding the disease's origins, symptoms, progression, consequences, and therapy. False, incomplete, or damaging views and attitudes around bipolar illness are prevalent in society and should be avoided.

Bipolar disorder is an illness that has been characterized and understood by many labels and methods throughout history. Bipolar illness has evolved throughout time, with modifications and breakthroughs in diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. Therefore, our proposals are:

Examining the history of bipolar illness may help us better understand its origins, causes, and consequences. The volume and breadth of studies looking at the historical evolution of bipolar disorder should be enhanced.

Examining the history of bipolar illness may assist offer a more objective evaluation of the efficacy, safety, and side effects of treatment options. The findings of study on the historical development of approaches used to treat bipolar illness should be considered while selecting and implementing treatments.

Examining the history of bipolar disorder may give more detailed information regarding societal perception, acceptance, and support for the condition. The results of research looking into the historical history of bipolar illness should be utilized to create disease awareness, education, and support services.

Bipolar disorder is a spectrum condition with many kinds, subtypes, and symptoms. Bipolar disorder must be grouped in order to improve diagnosis, treatment, and illness monitoring. Therefore, our proposals are:

Bipolar disorder should be classified according to clinical symptoms, severity, duration, frequency, cycle, and comorbidities. When classifying bipolar disorder, worldwide diagnostic systems and recommendations (e.g., DSM-5, ICD-11, ISBD) should be used.

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When classifying bipolar disorder, the biological, genetic, neurochemical, neuroanatomical, and neurophysiological basis of the condition should all be considered. Bipolar disorder should be classified based on the findings and advancements of neuroscientific research.

When classifying bipolar disorder, psychological, cultural, environmental, and disease-related elements should all be considered. When classifying bipolar disorder, the results and suggestions of psychological, sociological, and anthropological studies should be considered.

Diagnostic criteria for bipolar disorder are critical for ensuring accurate, timely, and reliable diagnosis and treatment.

The diagnostic criteria for bipolar disorder should discriminate between distinct kinds, subtypes, and illness features. Bipolar disorder diagnosis criteria should be based on worldwide diagnostic systems and recommendations such as the DSM-5, ICD-11, and ISBD. - Comorbid illnesses, or other mental or physical ailments that occur concurrently with bipolar disorder, should also be included in the diagnostic criteria for bipolar disorder. Bipolar disorder diagnostic criteria should include acceptable procedures and instruments for comorbid condition diagnosis, treatment, and monitoring. - Early illness symptoms, risk factors, and protective factors should all be considered while developing diagnostic criteria for bipolar disorder. Bipolar disorder diagnostic criteria should include the required precautions and measures for illness prevention, early intervention, and recovery.

The manic episode is the most obvious and distinguishing symptom of bipolar disorder. Symptoms of mania include dramatic mood fluctuations, increased energy, rapid thinking and speaking, reduced need for sleep, enhanced self-confidence, disassociation from reality, poor judgment, and engaging in dangerous and destructive activities. A manic episode may be detrimental to the patient's quality of life, functioning, and relationships. Therefore, our proposals are:

When diagnosing a manic episode, the intensity, length, and frequency of changes experienced by the patient in areas such as mood, mind, speech, sleep, activity, behavior, perception, and judgment must be considered. When diagnosing a manic episode, aspects such

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as the patient's history, family history, concomitant disorders, medication usage, and stressors should all be considered.

The goal of treating a manic episode should be to safeguard the patient's physical and mental health, diminish manic symptoms, maintain the patient's safety and functioning, and give information and support to the patient and his or her family members. Manic episodes should be treated with medication, psychotherapy, psychosocial treatments, and electroconvulsive therapy.

In monitoring the manic phase, elements such as the patient's adherence to medication, side effects, attack prevention, illness coping abilities, social support network, and quality of life should be considered. To monitor the mania stage, measures such as patient and family feedback, self-report questionnaires, and clinical assessment scales should be employed.

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